

D2.3 Synthesis of EPIC-WE Outcomes

Results of the 12 interventions to identify good practices that demonstrate the value of cultural game jams and game-making in helix ecosystems

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
EPIC-WE	Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments
TH	Triple Helix
QH	Quadruple Helix
DBR	Design-Based Research
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
HEI	Higher Education Institution
CI	Creative Industry
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institution
LL	Living Lab
CLL	Cultural Living Lab
YC	Youth Citizen
CH	Cultural Hub
QH Cultural Hub	Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub
CGJ	Cultural Game Jam

Key Resources

- Cultural Game Prototypes, EPIC-WE Resource Site: <https://epic-we.au.dk/games>
- Published EPIC-WE Reports: <https://zenodo.org/communities/epicwe/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

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Executive Summary

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1. Executive Summary

EPIC-WE: *Empowered Participation in Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments* is a Horizon Europe project that investigates how game-making can become culture-making, enabling youth to engage creatively and reflectively with European cultural heritage and values. Through Cultural Game Jams held in Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, the project developed participatory and empowering models for cultural participation and innovation by connecting Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), Creative Industries (CIs), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), and youth as civic partners. This summary synthesises the project's results and outcomes concerning its research questions, developed models, interventions, methodology, and wider impacts.

1.1 Project Research Questions

Three research questions guided the project:

1. How can games be understood as significant culture and cultural worlds in their own right while also shaping identities, society, and our cultural world in beneficial/harmful ways?

2. How can CHIs (cultural heritage institutions) together with CIs (creative industries) facilitate cultural game jams to enable youth's widened and empowered participation in culture and cultural heritage through culture- and value-sensitive game-making?

3. How might young people come to see themselves as cultural game-makers and value-creators through game jamming with European cultures and values? What is the potential value of cultural game jams and helix systems for CHI, CI, youth, and European society?

These questions framed the design of interventions and informed the project's analytical focus on youth empowerment, collaborative and cultural partnerships and cross-sector innovation.

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1.2 Project Reporting Ecosystems

This report, part of WP2 advances and synthesises insights from previous project deliverables, while offering new perspectives, recommendations, and answers to the project's research questions, research objectives, and wider outcomes and impacts, as emphasised in the project's Grant Agreement (GA) Description of Action (DoA).

More specifically, this report synthesises the results and insights from the project's 12 interventions to identify good practices that demonstrate the value of Cultural Game Jams and game-making as culture-making in quadruple helix (QH) ecosystems. The report does not stand in isolation, but builds on and synthesises findings from earlier outputs. In particular, it draws on the good practices and systematic reviews conducted in WP2 (Costa et al., 2024a; Costa et al., 2024b), which, among other insights, identified the absence of scholarly literature on Cultural Game Jams (D2.1 & D2.2). It further builds on the design and research protocols developed in WP3, focusing on the design of Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystems, QH Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and their research and facilitation (D3.1, D3.2 & D3.3). The report also incorporates the analyses conducted in WP4 on the operationalisation of Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams with youth (D4.1 & D4.2), as well as the project's impact assessment from WP6 (D6.4). In particular, this report has strong synergies with D4.1. While D2.3 provides a research synthesis of findings, analyses, and insights across the project's interventions and outcomes, D4.1 offers a practical, implementation-oriented perspective on those interventions.

In the following sections of the Executive Summary, the report first outlines the project's methodological approach and its core concepts that are primary theoretical and innovation outcomes: the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, Games for/through Culture, and youth's empowered participation. It then presents the main results and outcomes, linking them to the project's broader impacts and objectives and synthesising their relevance for stakeholders. Finally, the report

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offers key recommendations and suggests directions for future research and innovation.

1.3 Research and Methodology

The project employed Design-Based Research (DBR), combining iterative design with empirical inquiry. Data sources included observations, design artefacts, surveys, interviews, and digital traces. Analyses focused on cultural and value integration in game design and prototyping, intervention dynamics, and youth empowerment. DBR cycles informed CGJ Kit refinement, facilitation strategies, and scalability models, ensuring that insights were grounded in practice while contributing to theory on participatory cultural innovation. Through the DBR processes, vital conceptual, practical, and framework outcomes include the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and the QH Cultural Hubs; Cultural Game Jams and the CGJ Model and Kit to plan and facilitate them; the design and analytical lenses of Games for/through Culture; and frameworks and processes for youth's empowered participation.

1.4 The Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem

EPIC-WE adapts the Quadruple Helix (QH) innovation ecosystem (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012, 2022) to the cultural-creative domain, drawing inspiration from Living Labs and developing and enacting QH Cultural Hubs in Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024; Schütz et al., 2019). These QH Cultural Hubs explore and foster collaboration between CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth, positioning young people as co-creators and epistemic partners rather than end-users. The model integrates sector perspectives and ways of knowing across cultural heritage preservation and transformation, creative industry innovation, pedagogical frameworks, and civic agency to explore local and systemic cultural innovation. It demonstrates how cultural institutions can move beyond dissemination toward participatory co-creation.

1.5 Cultural Game Jams

Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) are the project's core design intervention. They transform cultural consumption into cultural production by inviting youth to create games inspired by cultural heritage, EU values, and broader cultural and

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societal themes. Unlike traditional game jams, CGJs emphasise cultural framing, reflective game-making, and value-sensitive design processes. Across twelve interventions, described here as the *local and glocal strands* – implemented either in national and local settings or across local and international (glocal) settings, CGJs demonstrated their potential, under particular contexts and conditions as integral to design-based methodologies, to enable youth to activate and express cultural heritage in new ways, foster creativity, and engage young participants as cultural agents in the co-creation of games that reflect, respond, and reimagine culture and the world around them. When carefully designed and facilitated, these interventions created spaces for negotiating and reimagining cultural narratives, experimenting with civic values through game-making processes, and exploring questions of belonging in the domains of culture and games. At the same time, these outcomes were neither automatic nor uniform, nor without challenges, but depended on contextual, institutional, and facilitative factors, which are taken up and discussed throughout this report. A key innovation of EPIC-WE is the design, implementation, and evaluation of the CGJ Model and Kit, presenting tangible resources for value-sensitive, culturally informed design and innovation through cross-sector game-making.

1.6 Games for Culture / Games through Culture

The project developed and implemented two complementary concepts and approaches for theorising, designing, and analysing cultural game prototypes that emerged through the project:

- **Games through culture:** Heritage becomes a tangible design material, with artefacts, stories, and collections reinterpreted into interactive forms.
- **Games for culture:** Games address intangible cultural issues, identity, justice, and sustainability through game design. Together, these modes illustrate how game-making mediates cultural heritage and narratives, enabling civic dialogue and positioning games as cultural worlds rather than just entertainment.

1.7 Youth's Empowered Participation

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The EPIC-WE project demonstrates that CGJs embedded in QH Cultural Hubs are novel and effective formats for participatory cultural innovation, youth empowerment, and value-sensitive game design. Synthesising twelve local and glocal CGJ interventions, youth's empowered participation connects to three key insights.

First, CGJs enable youth to move from cultural-creative consumers to active participants as game-makers, culture-makers, and civic actors. Public exhibitions, culturally reflective game design, and Youth Advisory Boards exemplified their contributions as highly relevant in creating and supporting youth belonging, agency, and empowerment in past and present cultural heritage, as well as in relation to EU values. Empowerment was strongest when youth were scaffolded in their roles but retained creative agency and autonomy, reflectively engaging with heritage and values as equal partners. Second, participation fostered shifts in self-perception and identity. Youth reported increased confidence, civic awareness, and cultural-creative agency, particularly when they experienced multiple CGJ roles, pushed their comfort zones, and successfully created innovative games through/for culture under time pressure. Third, formalised participation through Youth Advisory Boards (YABs) and the QH Cultural Hubs, integrating cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, higher education institutions, and youth, proved vital for sustaining engagement and empowerment. These structures facilitated cross-sector dialogue, iterative reflection, and co-creation, enabling youth to develop cultural, creative, and technical skills, engage meaningfully with European heritage and values, and become epistemic and practical partners in the iterative design of CGJs and games for/through culture.

1.8 Main Results and Outcomes

- Games as cultural worlds: Analysis of cultural game prototypes revealed strong cultural embedding, heritage remixing, value negotiation, and the creation of speculative and desirable futures, demonstrating how games through/for culture enable cultural engagement, reflection, and imagination.

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- Youth empowerment and identity development: Evidence from interviews and surveys showed shifts in self-perception, alongside increased confidence, civic awareness, and cultural-creative agency.
- Quadruple Helix collaboration: CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth successfully co-created inclusive cultural ecosystems, though sustaining engagement beyond jams remains a challenge.
- Methodological innovation: QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs evolved into a validated model and toolkit combining cultural framing, reflective prompts, and adaptive facilitation, tested across diverse Cultural Hubs and CGJ contexts.
- Scalability and transferability: Glocal CGJs confirmed modular design principles and adaptability for transnational replication.
- Institutional impact: CHIs reported renewed relevance and youth engagement; CIs explored new cultural markets and stakeholders; HEIs integrated CGJs into curricula.

1.9 Wider Impacts and Project Objectives

EPIC-WE addressed its objectives as follows:

- **ASSESS:** Demonstrated cultural and civic potential of game-making through empirical evidence of youth empowerment and integration of cultural heritage and values in games.
- **INNOVATE:** Developed and validated the CGJ model and kit within QH Cultural Hubs and ecosystems, creating new models for cultural participation and innovation.
- **TRANSFER:** Produced open-access resources (toolkits, resource site, protocols, guidelines) enabling replication by CHIs, educators, and creative practitioners.
- **SCALE:** Piloted glocal CGJs, capacity building workshops, and policy dialogues, informing strategies for embedding game-making as a cultural practice across Europe.

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These achievements contribute to EU priorities on cultural sustainability, democratic participation, and youth engagement, offering a replicable ecosystem and model for cultural innovation through game-making.

1.10 Stakeholder Relevance: Policy-Makers, CHIs, and CIs

EPIC-WE demonstrates how game-making can serve as a strategic lever for cultural participation, innovation and youth engagement. For policymakers, the project offers evidence-based models for embedding participatory cultural practices into European cultural heritage and values, as well as educational and industry agendas, aligning with priorities in inclusion and diversity, digital creativity, democratic participation, and civic empowerment. For Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs), CGJs provide a scalable approach to remediating and revitalising heritage through co-creation, fostering relevance among younger audiences. For Creative Industries (CIs), the framework opens new pathways to cultural partners and collaborative formats that combine cultural depth with interactive media. The validated Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem and QH Cultural Hub model ensures empowered collaboration, positioning youth as active cultural agents rather than passive consumers.

1.11 Main Recommendations

1. Embed Cultural Game Jams in Policy Frameworks

Support CGJs as a recognised model for cultural participation and youth empowerment within EU cultural and educational strategies.

2. Institutionalise Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

Encourage CHIs, CIs, and HEIs to adopt QH-based collaboration models and establish QH Cultural Hubs to ensure sustainable co-creation ecosystems beyond project timelines.

3. Invest in Open Resources and Capacity Building

Fund dissemination and training initiatives to strengthen and scale the CGJ model and methodologies across Europe, enabling replication in diverse cultural contexts.

4. Foster Cross-Sector Partnerships

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Incentivise partnerships between cultural institutions, creative industries, and educational actors to integrate game-making into culture and educational programmes and curricula.

5. Support Research on Cultural Games, Game-making as Culture-making, and Civic Engagement

Continue funding interdisciplinary research on games as cultural worlds and the creation of games through and for culture, focusing on their role in cultural heritage, potential in game innovation, driver in identity formation, value negotiation, and democratic dialogue.

1.12 Limitations and Future Directions

While EPIC-WE successfully demonstrated the cultural and civic potential of game-making, challenges remain in sustaining engagement beyond short-term interventions, institutionalising practices within CHIs and CIs, and ensuring equitable access across diverse socio-economic contexts. Future work should explore policy frameworks for long-term adoption, integration into cultural heritage, creative industries, formal education, and scalable digital infrastructures to support transnational cultural game-making ecosystems.

Introduction

02

2. Introduction

EPIC-WE: *Empowered Participation in Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments* is a Horizon Europe research and innovation project that investigates how game-making can become a form of culture-making, empowering young people to engage reflectively and creatively with European heritage and values. The project responds to urgent cultural and societal challenges: declining youth participation in cultural life, the need for inclusive and democratic cultural innovation, and the increasing influence of digital games as cultural artefacts and civic technologies (Grant Agreement, 2023).

Games are more than entertainment media; they are cultural worlds that shape identities, values, and imaginaries (Costa et al., 2025; Sicart, 2011, 2023; Holflod et al., 2024). They mediate how individuals experience heritage, ethics, and social norms, influencing both personal and collective narratives and experiences. Recognising this, EPIC-WE positions CGJs as design interventions that transform cultural consumption into cultural production and imagination. These game jams are embedded within an adapted quadruple helix innovation ecosystem (Carayannis & Campbell, 2012, 2022) positioned in the cultural domain and enacted through establishing QH Cultural Hubs that bring together cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), higher education institutions (HEIs), and youth as civic partners across local and glocal sites. This collaborative QH Cultural Hub model is designed to enable the co-design of new practices for cultural and value-sensitive participation, game-making and innovation.

The rationale for emphasising local and glocal QH Cultural Hubs lies in the dual necessity of context sensitivity and transnational connectivity. Local Cultural Hubs anchor interventions in tangible and intangible cultural heritage and community practices, while glocal elements connect them through shared themes, coordinated events, digital infrastructure, and collaboration frameworks. This reflects EPIC-WE's dedication to civic and cultural sustainability, engagement, and innovation at multiple levels, aligning with

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European priorities such as the New European Bauhaus, the European Youth Strategy, and the Sustainable Development Goals.

2.1 Report Structure

This report is organised into nine sections and report references, offering a comprehensive overview of the EPIC-WE project's aims, theoretical bases, interventions, and outcomes. The structure is designed to guide readers from a general overview of the project's aims to detailed analyses and actionable recommendations.

Section 1 – Executive Summary

Provides a clear overview of the project's aim, research questions, conceptual frameworks, methodology, and key findings. It emphasises the main concepts, outcomes, and recommendations for stakeholders.

Section 2 – Introduction

Establishes the context for the report by outlining the aims of research and innovation, guiding theories, and intended audiences. It defines the scope and boundaries of the work and introduces key concepts central to EPIC-WE, including the Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and the dual framing of Games for Culture / Games Through Culture. This section also presents examples of good practices that informed the design of interventions.

Section 3 – Methodology

Describes the Design-Based Research (DBR) approach adopted by the project, detailing data production methods, sources, and analytical frameworks. It also reflects on lessons learned from iterative design cycles and methodological adaptations across different contexts.

Section 4 – Local Strand Analysis

Provides an in-depth synthesis of local Cultural Game Jam interventions carried out in Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum. Each QH Cultural Hub's insights are presented in dedicated subsections, followed by cross-hub reflections that identify common patterns and differences within contexts.

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Section 5 – Glocal Strand Analysis

Examines Cultural Game Jam interventions that connected QH Cultural Hubs across national boundaries, conceptualised as distributed cultural Living Labs. This section analyses how glocal Cultural Game Jam promoted cultural exchange, collaborative creativity, and methodological scalability.

Section 6 – Comparative Strand

Integrates findings from local and glocal strands to provide a comparative perspective. It addresses the progression from local immersion to glocal connectivity, youth participation, empowerment, and cultural agency, methodological and pedagogical insights, and the broader outcomes and impacts of EPIC-WE. Meta-level reflections conclude this section.

Section 7 – Ethical Considerations

Outlines the ethical principles guiding the project, including informed consent, ethics, and situational and relational considerations in collaborative design contexts.

Section 8 – Limitations

Highlights methodological constraints, contextual variability, and gaps experienced during the project. It also considers the implications for future iterations and scaling.

Section 9 – Conclusion and Recommendations

Synthesises the project's contributions and proposes actionable recommendations for policymakers, cultural institutions, creative industries, and higher education institutions. These recommendations aim to support and strengthen the integration of cultural game-making into European cultural, innovative, and educational ecosystems.

2.2 Research and Innovation Aims

EPIC-WE examines and advances four interrelated objectives:

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- **O1 (ASSESS):** Explore the potential of games and game-making practices to empower youth and strengthen European values and cultural participation.
- **O2 (INNOVATE):** Design, develop, and validate a framework for Cultural Game Jams within quadruple helix ecosystems.
- **O3 (TRANSFER):** Produce accessible resources that enable organisations to replicate the Cultural Game Jam across Europe.
- **O4 (SCALE):** Equip actors with knowledge, skills, and policy instruments to embed game-making as a cultural and civic practice in institutional and policy infrastructures.

These aims position EPIC-WE at the intersection of design-based research, cultural heritage studies, creative sector innovation, and youth civic engagement, contributing to European innovation agendas and cultural policy frameworks. With [the EPIC-WE Resource Site](#), the project complies with Open Access standards and shares resources, materials, and insights with the public.

2.3 Guiding Theories, Approaches, and Questions

The project is based on Design-Based Research (DBR), which combines iterative design with empirical inquiry to produce actionable knowledge in real-world settings (Barab & Squire, 2004; McKenney & Reeves, 2019). DBR's iterative cycles of 1) analysis and exploration, 2) design and construction, and 3) evaluation and reflection, which lead to the dual outcomes of intervention maturation and theoretical understanding, enable EPIC-WE to design, prototype, test, evaluate, and adapt QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs while developing theoretical and practical frameworks for participatory cultural innovation.

Three research questions guide the inquiry:

- **RQ1:** How can games be understood as significant culture and cultural worlds in their own right while shaping identities, society, and cultural narratives in beneficial or harmful ways?

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- **RQ2:** How can CHIs and CIs facilitate cultural game jams to enable youth's widened and empowered participation in culture and heritage through value-sensitive game-making?
- **RQ3:** How might young people come to see themselves as cultural game-makers and value-creators through game jamming with European cultures and values? What is the potential value of cultural game jams and helix systems for CHIs, CIs, youth, and European society?

These questions draw on theories of game jams, participatory design, value-sensitive design, and cross-sector cultural innovation, as well as scholarship on games as artefacts with culture, ethics, and values (Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2014; Sicart, 2011, 2023). This synthesis combines insights from twelve CGJ interventions across local and glocal strands, translating research results into, on the one hand, tested ecosystems, models, and frameworks, and, on the other hand, practical methods, kits, and recommendations. It addresses the need for design-based evidence-driven models that show how CGJs can promote youth empowerment, cultural participation and co-creation through culture- and value-sensitive innovation. By presenting patterns, divergences, and lessons learned, the report offers a basis for adopting and scaling this approach within cultural, educational, and industry ecosystems.

2.4 Intended Audience

The report is designed for multiple stakeholders:

- Policymakers and creative-cultural stakeholders, seeking insights and models for inclusive cultural innovation aligned with EU priorities.
- Cultural heritage institutions and creative industries, exploring participatory and co-creative approaches to engage youth, diversify cultural value chains, and novel approaches to audience engagement.
- Educators and researchers, interested in integrating game-making into curricula and education and advancing design-based methodologies across diverse stakeholders.
- Youth organisations and civic actors, interested in democratic participation and cultural agency, and civic empowerment.

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2.5 Scope and Boundaries

The synthesis focuses on integrating results and findings from the project's design interventions (Cultural Game Jams), the collaborative infrastructure (quadruple helix innovation ecosystems and QH Cultural Hubs), the games developed during the project (games for culture and games through culture), as well as the local, glocal, and transnational collaborations and their outcomes within EPIC-WE's local and glocal QH Cultural Hubs. The report highlights the cultural, creative, designerly, and civic aspects of game-making, situates the findings within broader theoretical and policy contexts, responds in particular to the project's objectives and research questions, and also addresses wider impacts and outcomes. The report builds on the analytical processes of two work packages in EPIC-WE, namely WP4 (local analysis) and WP2 (glocal analysis).

2.6 Introduction to Main Concepts

2.6.1 Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs (QH Cultural Hubs) in EPIC-WE are place-based environments where cultural innovation is co-created by four sectors: higher education, cultural heritage, the creative industries, and youth citizens. They build on the EPIC-WE adaptation of the quadruple helix (QH) innovation ecosystem, initially formulated by Carayannis and Campbell (2012, 2022; Schütz et al., 2019), which expands traditional triple helix models by positioning civil society, culture, and media-based publics as central actors in knowledge production and knowledge democracy. Each hub, located in Óbidos, Hilversum, and Aarhus, translates these principles into local practice by creating infrastructure that supports shared cultural research, design, innovation, and decision-making across sectors.

The chosen method for enacting the QH ecosystem is based on Living Labs (LLs). Influenced by Scandinavian participatory and democratic design traditions, Living Labs provide a methodological foundation for iterative, real-world experimentation. As mentioned in the wider LL literature (e.g., Fuglsang et al., 2021; Schuurman et al., 2015; Steen & van Bueren, 2017; von Hippel, 2006),

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LLs support co-creation, multi-method inquiry, and user-driven innovation. In EPIC-WE, Living Lab practice is therefore how the QH ecosystem becomes operational, embedding research and innovation within everyday cultural contexts and engaging citizens as partners in the creation, testing, and refinement of cultural heritage innovations.

Through this combination of a conceptual QH cultural ecosystem and a methodological Living Lab approach, the QH Cultural Hubs serve as hybrid spaces – as cultural living labs – that support long-term, transdisciplinary collaboration. Cultural Hub coordinators facilitate dialogue and shared authority through ‘meetings in the middle’, ensuring that youth and other civil society actors transition from peripheral consultation to recognised co-creation, in line with research emphasising the vital role of citizen participation and open, reciprocal interaction in QH ecosystems (Schütz et al., 2019; Taratori et al., 2021). Over the project’s first two years, this integrated model has enabled partners to collectively explore, reinterpret and innovate cultural heritage across sectors and QH Cultural Hubs. Game-making as a form of culture-making has been central to this process, enabling the QH Cultural Hubs to create lasting cultural innovation and value while supporting broader European cultural policy objectives.

2.6.2 Cultural Game Jams (CGJs)

Within EPIC-WE, CCJs are the primary format and design intervention for enabling young citizens (ages 16–25) to participate meaningfully in cultural innovation. Rooted in the project’s Quadruple Helix (QH) cultural ecosystem and cultural Living Lab (LL) methodology, CGJs constitute real-world environments where young people collaborate with peers and partners across disciplines and sectors to create games using cultural heritage. In this context, game-making becomes culture-making: participants interpret, reimagine, integrate, and transform cultural heritage through game design, thereby cultivating cultural agency and contributing to emerging cultural narratives.

The CGJ positions youth as active contributors within the QH Cultural Hubs. Through game-making, young participants engage with cultural heritage institutions, the creative industries, and higher education partners, exploring

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cultural and societal themes and challenges through imaginative, hands-on processes. The EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit (CGJ Kit) supports these activities by offering models, methods, and tools that enable participants to create games through and for culture. By recognising games as legitimate forms of cultural expression, the project highlights games' capacity to reflect, remediate, integrate, and innovate cultural heritage, thereby strengthening youth participation in contemporary cultural life.

Insights from the EPIC-WE Systematic Literature Review (Costa et al., 2025) highlight that CGJs offer a unique approach that links game-making with cultural engagement and civic participation. Unlike traditional game jams, CGJs emphasise cultural imagination, interpretation, integration, and transformation, enabling participants to explore cultural heritage and European values in ways that are both culturally inventive and reflective. By integrating CGJs into the broader QH cultural ecosystem and enacting them through Living Lab approaches, EPIC-WE fosters environments that promote inclusive, innovative, and co-creative cultural development. In this way, CGJs serve as concrete exemplifications of the project's wider goals by enabling young people to co-shape cultural heritage and to actively imagine and co-create cultural futures.

2.6.3 Games for Culture / Games through Culture

A central outcome of CGJs in EPIC-WE is the creation of games rooted in culture and serving cultural purposes. These approaches illustrate how young people interact with cultural heritage and envision cultural futures by developing games that express unique forms of cultural imagination and engagement. Through the CGJs, youth develop and present games through culture and games for culture, which serve multiple purposes: as creative-artistic cultural expressions by youth, as concrete outcomes of the CGJs, and as collected research objects.

Games through culture use tangible cultural heritage as a concrete material for creative expression. Instead of only using games to communicate or educate about heritage, this approach views heritage as an active and direct source for game-making (Costa et al., 2025; Holflod et al., 2024). Young participants engage with artefacts, sites, archives, and collections from cultural heritage

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institutions, using them as prompts for the game's narrative, aesthetics, or mechanics throughout their game-making process. In this context, cultural heritage becomes both a conceptual and concrete material. In CGJs, cultural heritage institutions shift from custodianship to collaboration, supporting game design processes, sharing heritage expertise, and enabling young people to reinterpret and integrate heritage in contemporary and personally meaningful ways. Games through culture thus empower youth to become cultural creators by engaging deeply with existing heritage and reshaping it through creative practice.

Games for culture shift the focus from tangible heritage to broader cultural and societal themes. Here, game-making becomes a way to explore identity, belonging, values, and current issues. Youth examine intangible cultural themes and values such as community, citizenship, justice, democracy, or climate change and create games that articulate new cultural perspectives or imagine alternative futures. In this approach, game-making is value-oriented and reflective (Costa et al., 2025; Eriksson et al., 2024), with youth developing games that address contemporary issues, contribute to public dialogue, and express personal or collective dreams or concerns. Cultural and creative industry partners provide methods, tools, mentorship, and spaces where youth can develop their social or cultural visions into interactive experiences that enable players to experience and engage with them.

Games are cultural artefacts that both express and shape values, identities, and worldviews – and are vital parts of popular culture and the ever-expanding cultural legacy (Barwick et al., 2011). They provide interactive game worlds where players can explore and reflect on ethical questions, social themes, and notions of cultural belonging. Beyond entertainment, games can foster empathy, promote inclusion, and give voice to perspectives that are often marginalised. Considering that a large proportion of European youth regularly play games (Costa et al., 2025), their cultural significance and potential are profound and far-reaching.

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EPIC-WE expands this potential by enabling young people to create games that integrate and transform cultural heritage (Eriksson et al., 2024). The distinction between games through culture and games for culture clarifies two complementary ways of cultural participation and innovation. Games through culture reinterpret and integrate tangible heritage by engaging collections, artefacts, and historical narratives as game-making material. Games for culture address intangible values and societal themes by speculating, reflecting, provoking, or engaging with our cultural heritage. Together, these approaches and concepts articulate how game-making becomes a form of cultural imagination and expression. By designing games through culture and for culture, youth engage with heritage, contribute to emerging cultural narratives, and actively participate in shaping cultural values and visions.

2.6.4 Local and Glocal CGJ Interventions

EPIC-WE explores, designs, tests, and evaluates both local and glocal CGJ interventions that share multiple similarities but also diverge in specific ways.

Local CGJ interventions are tied to specific places and contexts, developed within clearly defined cultural and social environments. In EPIC-WE, local CGJs were organised by individual QH Cultural Hubs, involving local stakeholders, materials, and themes. Their main aim was to preserve and engage with shared cultural heritage, tackle societal issues relevant to that community, and foster local cultural participation through game-making. Locality here highlights continuity and authenticity, where cultural practices and values are preserved and explored within a confined local hub environment and setting. The design approach is inward-looking: strengthening local traditions and enabling youth to critically interact with their immediate cultural setting.

Glocal CGJ interventions, by contrast, occupy an in-between space – neither purely local nor global. They represent a dynamic interplay where global ideas, themes, and issues are integrated with local practices, heritage, and values. Rather than treating global and local as opposites, glocalisation acknowledges their mutual constitution: global trends shape local practices, and local cultures influence global narratives. In EPIC-WE, glocal CGJs aim to create hybrid spaces for co-creation, where participants across QH Cultural Hubs collaborate on

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shared global cultural themes while adapting them to local cultural contexts. This approach fosters intercultural awareness, cross-border collaboration, and the negotiation of values across cultures. It moves beyond local preservation toward glocal reimagination, enabling youth to explore heritage while situating it within broader global flows.

Lastly, the report is structured around disseminating findings and insights across local and glocal strands, thus emphasising the first round of interventions, which were local, the second round, which were glocal, and, lastly, comparing and contrasting those findings and insights.

2.6.5 Good Practices

In complex, participatory, and culturally situated projects, distinguishing between good practices and best practices is vital for both conceptual clarity and practical guidance. Good practices can refer to strategies that have demonstrated positive value within specific contexts. They are rooted in the realities of the local setting, including histories, partnerships, and constraints that influence their implementation. Good practices are adaptable, capable of being reinterpreted or modified when applied in new environments, and they demonstrate meaningful outcomes, whether by fostering participation, collaboration, or creativity. They are often the result of reflective practice, iterative experimentation, and continuous learning, recognising that success depends on the particularities of the context. Drawing on Costa et al. (2017), we approach the concept of *good practice* as strategic actions and corresponding tactics for transformation that are documented and made transferable, relevant, and influential to multiple stakeholders. However, they are always situated within the complexities and diversities of particular contexts.

By framing practices as “good,” the focus shifts to their value as inspiring models rather than rigid templates, enabling flexibility and responsiveness to local circumstances. Best practices, in contrast, might imply greater universality and suggest an optimal approach that can be reproduced across different contexts with highly predictable results. They are framed as standardised, replicable, and normative solutions, representing what is deemed most effective based on existing evidence. Although such an approach may suit fields where

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processes and environments are stable and predictable, it can be limiting in cultural, educational, and participatory contexts. In these settings, variability, diversity, and relational complexity are inherent, meaning that practices successful in one context may not transfer seamlessly to another. Significantly, claims of best practices risk privileging dominant perspectives, limiting space for diversity, and underestimating the importance of local knowledge, cultural specificity, and emergent methods.

For projects like EPIC-WE, which engage youth as partners, involve committed cross-sector collaborations, and drive complex cultural-creative processes and innovations in authentic, real-world contexts, the language of good practices is more suitable. It signals a recognition that culture-making, game-making, creative processes, and participatory research are dynamic, situated, and contingent. Here, good practices promote sensitivity, flexibility, reflection, and continuous learning, rather than implying a single, universal method. They encourage practitioners to learn from past examples while interpreting and tailoring them to their own context. In this sense, good practices can inspire and support an inclusive, adaptable, and innovative cultural ecosystem – one that values exploration and experimentation, recognises multiple pathways and perspectives, and promotes meaningful participation without assuming universal applicability or prescriptive certainty.

Methodology

03

3. Methodology

The EPIC-WE project adopted a Design-Based Research (DBR) approach as its overarching methodological framework. DBR is particularly suited to complex, real-world educational and cultural contexts through its integration of theoretical inquiry and theory-development with iterative design, empirical testing, and the refinement of practical outcomes and design principles. Rather than isolating interventions in controlled environments, DBR embeds innovation within authentic settings, enabling researchers and practitioners to co-create solutions while producing transferable knowledge (Barab & Squire, 2004; Brown, 1992; Cobb et al., 2003; McKenney & Reeves, 2019).

In EPIC-WE, DBR served three interconnected purposes:

- Design and enactment of CGJs as participatory interventions within quadruple helix ecosystems (involving CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth).
- Empirical study of these interventions to evaluate their potential for empowering youth, encouraging cultural participation, and embedding European heritage and values in cultural-creative practices.
- Developing theories and innovations to deliver practical, scalable models for CGJs that can be adapted and expanded across various contexts.

The DBR process was developed through repeated iterative and recursive cycles of 1) analysis and exploration, 2) design and construction, and 3) evaluation and reflection, leading to both intervention maturity and new theoretical insights, covering both local and glocal interventions. Each cycle informed the next, enabling the project to adapt in response to emerging insights, stakeholder feedback, and contextual constraints. This both iterative and recursive approach ensured that the interventions were not predetermined or fixed but evolving cultural laboratories aligned with the project's objectives: ASSESS, INNOVATE, TRANSFER, and SCALE (Grant Agreement, 2023).

3.1 Data Production Methods and Sources

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The CGJs were underpinned by a robust, iterative research design outlined in Research Protocol 3: EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Somers Miles et al., 2024) and subsequently refined (Somers Miles et al., 2025), ensuring systematic, ethical, and comparable data collection before, during, and after each event. Baseline surveys captured participant demographics, expectations, skills, and prior experiences, providing a reference point across iterations. During the interventions, a mixed-methods approach documented CGJ's lived experiences, facilitation practices, and decision-making processes through structured observations, youth game logs, and real-time reflections, including vox pops and video testimonials. Post-event surveys, collaborative reflections, and reflection sprints with QH Cultural Hub teams supported iterative evaluation and learning. The results were integrated into subsequent CGJs, while cultural game prototypes and devlogs (Game Logs) published on itch.io served as central analytical artefacts.

Across all DBR phases, ethical considerations guided both procedural practices, including GDPR compliance and informed consent, and situational ethics that supported youth agency and inclusive participation. Analysis was conducted through three complementary frameworks, Event Case Study Analysis, Local Thematic Analysis, and Local Games Analysis, which were later further analysed, compared and contrasted to create a synthesised analysis across local CGJs to articulate cross-hub findings (WP2; T2.4), enabling each CGJ to be examined as particular situated practice, an interpretive thematic corpus of sources, and sets of games prototypes as cultural artefacts. Together, these layers provided an integrated understanding of how empowered participation, cultural heritage and values, and societal themes and issues were expressed across the twelve CGJs and how empirical insights fed directly into the redesign of subsequent CGJ interventions. Overall, data production was multimodal and multi-sited, reflecting the CGJs as a socio-technical and cultural phenomenon. The following list outlines the key data sources included in the project's studies.

- Observational Data: Field notes, video recordings, and photographic documentation of game jam activities, facilitation practices, and participant interactions.

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- Design Artefacts: Game prototypes, concept sketches, and reflective game logs produced by participants during jams.
- Surveys and Questionnaires: Pre- and post-event instruments capturing participants' motivations, experiences, perceived learning outcomes, and attitudes toward cultural heritage and European values.
- Interviews and Focus Groups: Semi-structured conversations with youth participants, facilitators, and stakeholders from CHIs, CIs, and HEIs to explore perceptions of collaboration, cultural integration, and empowerment.
- Digital Trace Data: Contributions on shared platforms (Discord, Itch.io), including discussions, uploads, and feedback exchanges during local and glocal jams.
- Stakeholder Documentation: Internal reports, meeting notes, and evaluation forms from partner institutions.

This triangulation of data sources enabled a rich, layered, and multifaceted understanding of both processes and outcomes, thereby strengthening validity through methodological diversity.

3.2 Analytical Frameworks

Analysis – in both local and glocal instances – combined qualitative and reflexive thematic and design retrospective analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Cobb et al., 2003; Edelson, 2002) through interplays between deductive and inductive coding, both semantic and latent, and retrospective and prospective analysis and design, guided by three complementary analytical approaches to examine the outcomes and processes of the CGJs:

1. Game Analyses (Value-Sensitive Game Design Perspective)

Focused on the cultural and civic dimensions of the cultural game prototypes, this approach examined how heritage and European values were represented, negotiated, and embedded in the games through/for culture concepts, narratives, and mechanics. It assessed the depth of cultural integration and the extent to which civic themes were operationalised through game design choices.

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2. Intervention Analyses (Retrospective Evaluation and Prospective Design)

This approach examined CGJs as interventions within quadruple helix ecosystems, considering both retrospective assessments and prospective design implications. It investigated facilitation strategies, collaborative infrastructures, and adaptive processes, analysing how CHIs, CIs, and HEIs co-designed and iteratively refined the CGJs to promote inclusivity, creativity, and cultural participation.

3. Thematic Analyses (Cross-Cutting (Local/Glocal) Insights)

Drawing on diverse qualitative and quantitative data sources, this approach synthesised patterns across QH Cultural Hubs and thematic strands to identify overarching themes across the local and glocal interventions. It focused on participation and empowerment, examining youth agency, role-taking, and identity formation as cultural game-makers, while also tracing systemic dynamics of collaboration and cultural engagement across local and glocal contexts.

Cross-case syntheses were utilised to identify patterns, divergences, and transferable principles across local and glocal strands. This approach aligns with DBR's dual commitment to the contextual relevance of interventions and to theoretical understanding and generalisability.

Local Strand Analysis

04

4. Local Strand Analysis

The local strand of EPIC-WE focuses on how CGJs unfold within specific cultural and institutional settings, treating each CGJ as a distinct situated living laboratory for exploring the project’s research questions in practice. These local interventions foreground the relational and organisational work through which cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), and higher education institutions (HEIs) collaborate to create meaningful conditions for youth to engage with culture not as passive audiences, but as active co-creators and cultural actors. By grounding game-making in local contexts, collections, and partnerships, the CGJs make visible how cultural values, heritage, and societal themes are negotiated through game-making processes.

Across the local CGJs, several shared lessons emerged regarding the design and facilitation of participatory game-making environments. Adaptive facilitation structures, careful orchestration of physical spaces, and thoughtful sequencing of activities proved crucial for sustaining creative flow and protecting uninterrupted periods for cultural ideation and prototyping. Decisions about locations, material resources, and transitions between sites, such as museums, schools, and studios, directly shaped participants’ capacity to collaborate and remain engaged. In parallel, scaffolded reflection, flexible role-taking, and inclusive facilitation practices supported youth agency and deeper cultural engagement.

The overview table below summarises CGJ1 and CGJ2 across Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum, providing a shared point of reference for the subsequent local synthesis, which examines how these design choices shaped outcomes and sets the stage for the project’s cross-hub glocal insights into youth empowerment, cultural game-making, and cross-sector collaboration.

Table 1: Overview of Local CGJs

	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam 1			EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam 2		
	Aarhus	Óbidos	Hilversum	Aarhus	Óbidos	Hilversum

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Theme	Human Nature	Óbidos - UNESCO City of Literature	Open Choice	Contemporary and postmodern artworks	Óbidos Lagoon (SDGs 14 and 15)	Media & Democracy or Media & Equality
Location	ARoS, Aarhus	Creativity Square, Óbidos	NISV Media Museum	ARoS, Aarhus	Creativity Square, Óbidos	NISV Media Museum; X11 High School
Duration	3-4 th February 2024	6-9 th February 2024	13-14 th April 2024	7-8 th September	29 th April to 2 nd May 2024	9-13 rd September 2024
Participants	23 youth	26 youth	15 youth	39 youth	40 youth	61 youth
Games produced	5	9	4	9	14	15

The following synthesis explores how these design choices shaped outcomes in Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum, highlighting both the benefits and tensions of cultural game-making in glocal contexts. It sets the stage for cross-hub insights – the glocal strand – on how CGJs can empower youth, foster cultural game-making, and strengthen collaboration across sectors.

4.1 Synthesis of Local Interventions

4.1.1 Aarhus Local Insights

Table 2: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ#1, Human Nature)

Date: February 3–4, 2024

Location: ARoS, Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 2 days

Funded by
the European Union

Grant Agreement No 10109505

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Participants: 23 youth (ages 15–27, open recruitment)

Number of Games: 5 prototypes

Theme: Human Nature (Golden Age artworks from ARoS' permanent collection)

The first Aarhus CGJ 1 in Aarhus (Feb 3–4, 2024) brought together 23 youths at ARoS Art Museum to co-create games inspired by cultural heritage. Guided by art facilitators, participants explored the permanent exhibition “Human Nature,” focusing on its four thematic rooms: “Philosophy,” “Religion,” “Exploration,” and “Landscape,” and reinterpreted golden age artworks through game-making. The event was co-organised and evaluated by a CHI, CI, and HEI partner institution within the QH Cultural Hub. Five games were produced.

Table 3: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ2, ARoS Collection: 1960-now)

Date: September 7–8, 2024

Location: ARoS, Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 2 days

Participants: 39 youth participants (open recruitment plus one secondary school class)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes

Theme: Contemporary and postmodern artworks, ARoS Collection: 1960 - now

Aarhus CGJ 2 (Sept 7–8, 2024) engaged 39 youths in co-creating games through/for culture at ARoS Art Museum. This time, participants worked with contemporary and postmodern artworks from the ARoS collection: 1960–present, again supported by art facilitators. Partners included the three partners from the first CGJ and the Youth Advisory Board (YAB), all of which contributed to the design and evaluation of the vent. Nine games were produced. The YAB consisted of participants recruited from the first Aarhus CGJ, who had a particular interest in either games and culture, diversity and participation, or heritage and art. The YABs developed during the project’s lifetime, integrating additional youth from later CGJs and from project-adjacent areas, and, from the

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initial CGJs onward, were a vital part of the QH Cultural Hub, positioned as equal partners in research and innovation.

Games as Cultural Worlds and Identity-Shaping Forces (RQ1, Aarhus)

Games through/for culture, as evidenced by the CGJs, serve as both means of cultural engagement and engaging cultural worlds. Participants relate to and interact with games as expressive artefacts that convey shared heritage, critique societal norms, and enact values. The incorporation of European values, heritage, and societal themes (e.g., feminism, climate crisis, disability representation) into cultural game prototypes demonstrates how games through/for culture can both integrate and mediate cultural or societal values and narratives.

From an interpretive standpoint, games in the CGJs became cultural mirrors and lenses. They enabled youth to express and reflect on their own identities and roles, while also envisioning alternative futures. This duality, between reflection and projection, positions games as distinctive carriers of culture that reimagine the past, engage the present, and envision the future in interactive and experiential ways.

Participants voiced transformative experiences through their meetings with and perceptions of cultural heritage and values, indicating that games – as interactive media and something to be made – can reshape cultural awareness and identity formation. However, the local cases also reveal potential issues. Hierarchical team dynamics, uneven skill distribution, and confusion about cultural themes sometimes led to experiences of disempowerment or exclusion within the CGJ teams, especially among participants who were less experienced in game technologies or design. Moreover, the tension between traditional game jam expectations and the cultural heritage and value-sensitive framing of CGJs created dissonance for some, who struggled to reconcile their roles as coders with the call to become culture-makers.

Thus, game-making and games can in themselves become cultural worlds that lead to experiences of empowerment or disempowerment, depending on how they are presented, facilitated, and contextualised. Their potential issues emerge

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when cultural tensions or complexities are unacknowledged or underexplored, power is uneven, or when game-making or games themselves reinforce dominant bias, narratives, or identities without space for dissent or alternative voices. Their true potential, on the other hand, lies in fostering cultural, creative, and critical imagination, dialogue, and reflection both individually and collectively.

CHIs and CIs Facilitating Culture- and Value-Sensitive Game Jams (RQ2, Aarhus)

The CGJs demonstrate that collaboration between CHIs and CIs is essential for creating inclusive, empowering, and culturally rich game jam experiences. CHIs provide contextual depth and value, and access to cultural heritage sites, collections, and materials, while CIs contribute game design expertise, creative tools, and industry insight. This synergy enables a transdisciplinary space where youth can engage with culture not as passive consumers but as active co-creators. Facilitation emerged as a critical factor where the experiences of meaningful and effective facilitation involved:

- Scaffolded reflection (e.g., CGJ Kit, Game Logs, community infrastructure),
- Participants' flexible role-taking (e.g., CGJ Role Cards, switching between roles as designer, storyteller, artist, coder),
- Inclusive practices (e.g., accessibility accommodations, safe spaces),
- Cultural framing (e.g., game exhibitions, artwalks, city walks, cultural prompts).

However, the analyses also highlight challenges. Some participants felt overwhelmed by the amount and complexity of CGJ processes, methods, and tools – and a more comprehensive and compact CGJ Kit was developed to enable the creation of cultural game prototypes, or provide participants with more clarity in relation to the cultural framing. Other participants wanted more structure and guidance as they struggled with the open-ended format. These tensions suggest that CHI–CI collaborations must be continuously adaptive, offering differentiated CGJ pathways and processes, and tailored support based on participants' backgrounds, motivations, and needs.

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Youth as Cultural Game-Makers and Value-Creators within CGJs and Helix Systems (RQ3, Aarhus)

The CGJs show that youth start to see themselves as cultural game-makers and value-creators when they are:

- Recognised as partners (not just students or specific disciplines such as coders)
- Experiencing creative agency – individually and collectively
- Engaged with cultural heritage creatively or critically
- Supported in integrating and reflecting on values

During the two local CGJs, participants expressed pride in their cultural game prototypes, saw their work as authentic cultural expressions, and reflected on how their games through/for culture engaged cultural heritage or addressed societal issues. This shift, from consumer to cultural creator and partner, was facilitated by the collaborative and reflective nature of the CGJs. Youth as culture-makers refer to the dynamic of them both exploring and relating to cultural heritage in new ways through CGJs, while creating collaborative and innovative expressions of cultural heritage through cultural game prototypes that enable them to experience, belong to, and reinterpret cultural heritage in their own voice and through their own creations.

The QH Cultural Hub model (including CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth) offers a systemic, transferable framework for sustaining such transformation. It enables:

- Cross-sector collaboration, enriching the cultural and creative ecosystems
- Youth empowerment, by positioning them as equal partners and co-creators of culture
- Cultural innovation, through the interplay of tangible and intangible heritage and creative game-making
- Cultural and societal engagement, as games become vehicles for dialogue, reflection, and education.

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For CHIs, CGJs provide a means to reinvigorate heritage, making it relevant and participatory, and discovering new interactive potentials for audience engagement. For CIs, they provide access to emerging talent (game-makers and culture-makers) and new game narratives, aesthetics, mechanics, and worlds (games through/for culture). For youth, they become a medium for identity exploration, skill development, cultural reflection, and empowerment. European society can support culture- and value-sensitive innovation, intercultural dialogue, and democratic participation in cultural heritage.

4.1.2 Óbidos Local Insights

Table 4: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ1, UNESCO City of Literature)

Date: February 6–9, 2024

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 26 youth (university students; ages 18–28)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (one made by Professors from Lusófona University)

Theme: Óbidos as UNESCO City of Literature

Óbidos CGJ1 took place in the Óbidos municipality from 6th to 9th February 2024, with a total of 26 participants aged 18-28 years. The theme of the game jam, "Óbidos Literary Town of UNESCO," focused on the cultural importance of literature. A total of nine games through/for culture were developed. The event was co-organised and evaluated by CHI (Óbidos Municipality), Lusófona University (HEI), and CI (Battlesheep).

Table 5: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ2, Óbidos Lagoon)

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Date: April 29 – May 2, 2024

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 40 youth (25 university students, 15 secondary school students, ages 15–25)

Number of Games: 14 prototypes

Theme: Sustainability and Biodiversity – Óbidos Lagoon, connecting to SDGs 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land)

Óbidos CGJ2 took place from April 29 to May 2 in Óbidos, Portugal, with the theme “Sustainability and Biodiversity – Óbidos Lagoon.” The event linked the lagoon’s cultural heritage and biodiversity to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). A total of 40 participants produced 14 games through/for culture. The event was co-organised and evaluated by CHI (Óbidos Municipality), Lusófona University (HEI), and CI (Battlesheep).

Games as Cultural Worlds and Identity-Shaping Forces (RQ1, Óbidos)

In Óbidos’ CGJ1, nine games through/for culture were produced. The process brought together video game students who received cultural preparation, consisting of introductory lectures, immersive historical tours, and visits to cultural institutions, to support and shape the cultural and creative outcomes of the games.

Three games in particular, Puss in Books and Walls of Colour, emerged directly from participants’ engagement with Óbidos’ local cultural heritage. In Puss in Books, inspired by the many cats seen around the village, players control a cat exploring stories within a library, typing words to control the cat's actions and unfold its narrative. Walls of Colour drew on the marked village walls observed during visits, transforming these regional details into a creative game concept. Similarly, the game In Search for Words reflected Óbidos’ literary identity, following a writer seeking inspiration amid writer’s block. Despite these successes, limitations emerged: as participants were not involved in selecting the theme, “Óbidos City of Literature” felt too abstract, making it difficult for some to connect the cultural theme to game design.

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Óbidos CGJ2 further advanced this integration of cultural heritage, framing game creation around the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land). By engaging with environmental themes through activities like the visit to the Óbidos Lagoon, participants gained a firsthand understanding of its ecological and cultural significance. This experience informed the mechanics, narratives, and aesthetics of their games, transforming global sustainability values into interactive, localised game experiences. For example, *Criminal Fauna Identification* asks players to identify the perpetrators of several “crimes” by giving them information about the local fauna’s habits and characteristics that they learned on their visit to the Lagoon. Similarly, *Otterway* uses the familiar aesthetics of local Óbidos culture (such as boats and fishing nets) along with local species to explore issues of proper waste disposal.

In total, Óbidos CGJ2 produced 11 games through/for culture, all of which addressed ecological and sustainable growth in some way. CGJ facilitators played a key role in guiding these reflections, ensuring that creative decisions aligned with ethical and context-sensitive principles, and providing critical information to guarantee the game’s cultural accuracy. In addition to the two previous examples, games such as *Blooming Shallows* explored the intricate process of promoting sustainable development while managing natural resources, and *Óbidoswatching* emphasised the difficulty of ensuring that natural heritage remains untouched. Meanwhile, games such as *Spirit of the Lake* and the aforementioned *Criminal Fauna Identification* relied on scientific information provided and fact-checked by these facilitators to work as cultural game prototypes. The above examples benefited from having more facilitators present, which led to more engaged participants and strengthened the game’s connection to both the theme and cultural heritage.

Together, the two CGJs demonstrated that games are cultural worlds that reflect, interpret, and shape societal values and themes. When framed through cultural and ethical lenses, games become powerful tools for engagement, education, and transformation, connecting identity, community, local heritage, and global awareness.

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CHIs and CIs Facilitating Culture- and Value-Sensitive Game Jams (RQ2, Óbidos)

The collaboration between Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs) and Creative Industries (CIs) in Óbidos CGJs demonstrated how structured facilitation and inclusive environments can foster meaningful youth engagement with culture and heritage. During Óbidos CGJ1 and CGJ2, the CHI partner, represented by Óbidos Municipality (CMO), served as organiser and cultural heritage facilitator, while the CIs, represented by Battlesheep (BS), served as game-making facilitators and HEIs (UL) acted as university students recruiters and researchers. Youth interacted with professionals from the game industry, academic researchers and lecturers, representatives from HEIs, and local government. They also engaged with representatives from cultural institutions, such as curators, historians, and small booksellers. Interactions were friendly, creating a welcoming atmosphere. Meals were shared between participants and facilitators, fostering a sense of belonging and community. The active involvement of facilitators played a key role: the pitch sessions fostered critical reflection as participants discussed how their games related to the CGJ theme and Óbidos' cultural heritage, and they actively engaged with and applied the facilitators' feedback. Two participants from Óbidos CGJ1 stated that interactions with heritage experts encouraged dialogue beyond what a lecture or online search could offer:

“Probably when we were visiting PIM,! [name of an exhibition at the gallery]. The expert was talking about people not reading as much anymore, so initially, we got some ideas about trying to convert our game into a sort of Tower Defence game, where you send things to people, but now it would be books for people to read.” (Youth Participant)

“I think the experience was completely different because we also had a lot of people talking to us, discussing literature with us. In fact, one of the mechanics of our game was precisely inspired by something one of the speakers mentioned to us.” (Youth Participant)

This led the youth to explore cultural heritage and values through game design and to feel confident in expressing their insecurities or doubts throughout the

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event, thanks to a supportive network. Moreover, in the case of Óbidos CGJ2, the diverse age group (15-25) and mixed educational backgrounds fostered peer-to-peer learning. Participants were initially hesitant but gradually gained confidence through interactions with facilitators. In this sense, CHIs, HEIs and CIs can facilitate empowered participation in CGJs by:

- Co-designing activities that blend cultural heritage education with creative freedom;
- Ensuring continuous facilitator engagement to provide both heritage and technical support;
- Encouraging cross-level collaboration between experienced and less experienced participants;
- Developing informal and equal relationships with youth;

Youth as Cultural Game-Makers and Value-Creators within CGJs and Helix Systems (RQ3, Óbidos)

Within the EPIC-WE project, CGJs serve as spaces for empowering youth in cultural participation, inviting them to create games through/for culture, positioning game-making as culture-making. During Óbidos CGJ1, this approach was embodied through activities that deeply connected participants with Óbidos' literary heritage identity. Pre-CGJ preparation included a lecture on the theme of the CGJ and an immersive tour of the village, visiting two libraries, the Óbidos Castle, a historical typesetting, and the Nova Ogiva art gallery. Cultural heritage experts guided these visits, sharing the story of Óbidos as a city of literature, the importance of independent bookstores and publishers, and the value of reading and physical books. To foster agency and cultural-creative exploration, participants were housed within the village centre, allowing them to continue engaging with the cultural heritage environment throughout the CGJ. This close engagement proved crucial for inspiration:

"I think the main mechanics we created for the game were inspired by the book creation process, and we drew inspiration when we visited the typography" - Youth Participant.

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“When we visited the Santiago bookstore, I immediately had the idea of what to model in 3D; it really represented what I envisioned for the project.” -Youth Participant.

Participants emphasised the difference between exploring a theme online and experiencing it through direct interaction with places, experts, and stories in their local real context. Survey results reflected this impact: participants reported a greater awareness of Óbidos’ culture, found the cultural activities meaningful for game design, and felt they had learned how to make games that celebrate culture.

Building on this foundation, Óbidos CGJ2 demonstrated how CGJs, supported by collaboration among Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Creative Industries (CI), and Higher Education Institutions (HEI), can empower youth as culture-makers and value-driven game-makers. Centred on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 14 (Life Below Water) and 15 (Life on Land), the CGJ invited participants to engage with sustainability and cultural identity through creative, experiential learning. Moreover, the cultural heritage facilitators were present throughout the CGJ, providing real-time feedback to participants.

Survey data confirmed strong positive engagement: 92% of Lusófona University students and 100% of Joséfa de Óbidos high school students reported that their expectations were met or exceeded. The pre-CGJ visit to the heritage-rich Óbidos Lagoon, cited by 69% as key to their creative process, helped participants connect local heritage with global sustainability themes. Motivations also varied: university students emphasised enjoyment, while high school participants valued gaining experience, reflecting the flexibility of the CGJ format in addressing diverse learning goals. Overall, 65% of all participants said they were very likely to recommend the CGJ event.

Through a combination of cultural heritage facilitation, game design mentorship, and collaborative teams, participants experienced game-making as a means for cultural participation and self-expression. Working with professionals and cultural experts, they not only developed game design skills but also learned how games can communicate heritage, values, shape identities, and contribute to

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European cultural participation and belonging. Together, the two CGJs show how collaboration around cultural heritage enables youth to see themselves not merely as players but as cultural agents, creators of meaningful, value-driven games that foster reflection, sustainability, and connection between local heritage identity and global cultural values.

4.1.3 Hilversum Local Insights

Table 6: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ1, Open Choice)
Date: April 13–14, 2024
Location: Media Museum, Hilversum, Netherlands
Duration: 2 days
Participants: 15 youth (open recruitment)
Number of Games: 4 prototypes
Theme: Open choice

Hilversum CGJ1 took place on 13–14 April 2024 at the Sound & Vision Media Museum. It ran as a 30-hour CGJ with 15 participants aged 20–27, who self-formed into teams and selected themes via a pre-survey; two teams focused on climate change, and two on mental health. Four games through/for culture were produced.

Table 7: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ2, Media, Democracy, and Equality)
Date: September 9–13, 2024
Location: X11 High School (Utrecht) & NISV Media Museum (Hilversum), Netherlands
Duration: 4 days, across one week
Participants: 61 youth (secondary school students, ages 16–18)
Number of Games: 15 prototypes
Theme: Choice between Media & Democracy or Media & Equality

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Hilversum CGJ2 ran 9–13 September 2024 in a hybrid school–museum format: X11 (Utrecht) and Sound & Vision (Hilversum). It involved two school classes, 61 participants aged 15–16 and focused on “media & democracy” and “media & social injustice.” Fifteen games through/for culture were produced

Games as Cultural Worlds and Identity-Shaping Forces (RQ1, Hilversum)

Across both CGJs, games functioned as cultural lenses more than directly remixing specific heritage materials. In CGJ1, the museum visit sparked cultural themes (e.g., social media, climate anxiety), but connections often remained surface-level in the final mechanics, partly because the audiovisual heritage collections were hard to productively “plug into” the prototyping of almost exclusively physical games. The museum inspired youth, but there was no deep integration of the cultural material into their games.

CGJ2 cultural game prototypes engaged a broad set of societal topics and values (oppression, inequality, democracy, racism), suggesting that game worlds were used to stage value conflicts and power dynamics; however, the integration of EU values was uneven and often remained declarative (stated in pitches or gamelogs) rather than clearly embodied in the game worlds, mechanics, or narratives.

The valuable side of games as cultural worlds appears when teams couple a clear theme with workable mechanics (e.g., resource trade-offs, decision-making under constraints) that prompt team reflection, dialogue, or perspective-taking. Limitations emerged when cultural complexity was under-analysed or when the game’s framing was shifted toward moralising messages without playable depth, risking disengagement or caricature. CGJ1’s tension between heritage inspiration and integration, and CGJ2’s tendency to “designate” values rather than integrate them, point to a recurring gap: the integration of cultural collections and EU values into mechanics and storytelling.

Identity-shaping effects were reported as participants navigated moral choices (happiness vs. climate goals; equality vs. advantage) and recognised how game mechanics reflected those choices; participants noted that expert feedback and

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playtesting helped them integrate EU values more deeply. Although in some cases the integration was weaker and remained at the pitch level.

CHIs and CIs Facilitating Culture- and Value-Sensitive Game Jams (RQ2, Hilversum)

In CGJ1, participants appreciated accessible heritage facilitation, collaborative rituals and exercises (heritage walks/brainstorming, Crazy 8s, and LEGO), and an open atmosphere; however, dense documentation tasks (gamelogs, forms, and photography) disrupted the creative flow, made it hard to keep up, and limited later analysis and reflective depth. This suggests that making documentation requirements lighter and more meaningfully embedded in the game design process, rather than a chore, could help participants recognise its value in game-making and produce higher-quality results.

CGJ2 highlighted the flexibility required in facilitation requirements between participant groups. With CGJ1 having participants from open recruitment and being more intrinsically motivated, and CGJ2 working with groups of high school students, where the CGJ was embedded in their mandatory programme. In CGJ2, the teachers had to take on a more prominent role in the facilitation process, especially in maintaining motivation. Having a diverse group of facilitators enabled smooth handovers and allowed differentiated support. In CGJ2, alternating between familiar (school) and unfamiliar (museum) spaces produced productive energy but was also perceived as disrupting the creative flow, as teams were deep into prototyping, indicating a need to plan shifts in location carefully and protect large windows of “just making”.

Across both CGJs, we see five facilitation considerations:

- Cultural heritage facilitation that goes beyond inspiration, providing concrete design aids (e.g., showing examples of how values are integrated into the mechanics of successful serious games). This should address the gap between being inspired by culture and incorporating it into the game design process.
- Role flexibility in the facilitation team depending on the participant’s age, background and experience.

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- Paying attention to team composition to mitigate possible skill asymmetries (pairing storytellers, coders, artists; having rotating leadership).
- Integrate documentation into the game design process: structured but brief reflection checkpoints tied to playtests and feedback moments rather than paperwork, to sustain game-making momentum while capturing cultural learning;
- Organise space, activities, materials, and potential shifts in location (e.g., moving from the museum to the school) to avoid fragmentation or disruption of creative flow and to protect uninterrupted windows for prototyping the games.

Youth as Cultural Game-Makers and Value-Creators within CGJs and Helix Systems (RQ3, Hilversum)

Evidence of empowerment is strongest when youth have experienced different CGJ roles within their team, have pushed their comfort zones, and have succeeded in creating testable prototypes under time pressure. CGJ1 participants reported pride in stepping outside comfort zones and learning to trust both their abilities and their teams', while maintaining creative agency.

In CGJ2, empowerment was more heterogeneous: some groups articulated clear takeaways and saw how the skills learned in the CGJ helped them in the future; others disengaged or questioned the usefulness of those skills, often when group dynamics were problematic or when the value of the experience remained abstract to them. This underscores the importance of flexible facilitation structures that adapt to participants' backgrounds. In both CGJs, participants confirmed that the current CGJ structures supported students' agency throughout the different phases of the CGJ model, from "we have an idea" to "people can actually play our prototype", helping them recognise themselves as makers, not just participants.

The CHI–CI–HEI collaboration provided access to cultural heritage spaces, expert feedback, and diverse game design tools; improved reach to participants with diverse skill sets and richer perspectives on cultural or societal topics and

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game jam design. To convert from a triple to a quadruple collaboration, including youth, the creation of a Youth Advisory Board (YAB) proved very useful. Members of the YAB were recruited from participants in GJ1 and should be included in the following cultural game jam design process at different levels: (a) being an integrated part of the CGJ process itself, for example by giving feedback to CHI and HEI on framing culture/values through more curated examples, (b) participating in the facilitation and research process during the CGJ, and (c) participating as experts or jury using the transition tools of the CGJ Kit.

4.2 Cross-Hub Local Insights

Across the three QH Cultural Hubs, Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum, a common theme emerges: games become cultural worlds that enable young people to examine cultural identity, values, and heritage. All QH Cultural Hubs show that when framing is meaningful and facilitation is inclusive, young people can turn game-making into processes of cultural participation, empowerment, and belonging. However, the extent of cultural integration varies.

Throughout the project, a consistent pattern emerges in how cultural themes are incorporated into game design. When participants are provided meaningful opportunities to engage with cultural heritage, whether through art, place-based experiences, archives, or thematic framing, the resulting games tend to reflect deeper links between cultural content and gameplay. However, challenges arise when cultural inspiration remains superficial, with heritage, values, or societal themes mentioned but not thoroughly integrated into the game. This gap between inspiration and integration underscores the need for stronger scaffolding (such as the CGJ Kit) to help participants transform cultural ideas into interactive, playable games through/for culture.

A cross-cutting challenge involves balancing creative freedom with structured support. All QH Cultural Hubs report tensions around facilitation, whether it's uneven skill distribution in Aarhus, the need for continuous mentorship in Óbidos, or disruptions to creative flows due to too many scheduled activities in Hilversum. These issues highlight a project-wide finding and opportunity for

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further research and innovation: refining CGJ models and facilitation frameworks to be adaptive, culturally grounded, and responsive to diverse participant needs. Innovations such as scaffolded processes, flexible role-taking, and youth advisory boards offer promising directions. Scaffolded processes can support participants in articulating experiences, values, and emerging insights at different levels of abstraction and comfort, helping to make reflective practices deeper and meaningful across age, expertise, and cultural backgrounds. Flexible role-taking enables participants to move between positions as creators, learners, facilitators, and critics, encouraging negotiation of participation rather than predefined roles and supporting shifts in agency over time.

Youth advisory boards, in turn, offer a more sustained form of youth participation that extends beyond the temporal boundaries of individual CGJ interventions, creating processes and spaces where young people can influence CGJ framing, decision-making, and evaluation processes, specifically, and the project initiatives, generally, and where their situated knowledge supports both design, facilitation, and joint reflection. Together, these approaches point towards participation models that foreground scaffolded game-making and co-agency, while remaining open to contextual adaptation and iterative development. Ultimately, the CGJs succeed best when they empower youth not just as coders or artists, but as cultural agents, co-creating games that reflect, critique, and reimagine heritage and the world around them.

The three QH Cultural Hubs collectively demonstrate how games through/for culture can be understood as meaningful cultural worlds (RQ1) capable of shaping identities and societal narratives in both positive and negative ways. Positively, games through/for culture enabled youth to explore cultural heritage and complex themes, such as feminism, the Anthropocene, sustainability, belonging, and democracy, through cultural-creative expression and critical reflection. Negatively, when cultural framing was vague or facilitation and scaffolding were less integrated throughout the CGJs, games risked reinforcing dominant narratives or disengaging participation. The dual role of games as mirrors and lenses of cultural heritage was most effective when heritage and values were built into the mechanics and storytelling, rather than just declared

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in pitches. Regarding facilitation (RQ2), the analysis highlights the importance of CHI–CI close collaboration in creating inclusive, empowering environments. CHIs contributed cultural depth and access to heritage, while CIs provided support for game design processes, game-making mentorship, and creative tools. Successful facilitation relied on adaptable structures, scaffolded processes, and informal, trust-building interactions. In this context, scaffolded processes concern cultural heritage reflection that is not postponed to the end of the process or limited to documentation activities, but rather an active, facilitatory part of key design choices and processes, with deep integration of cultural heritage and values into the participants' workflows.

Finally, youth empowerment (RQ3) was most evident when participants were enabled and recognised as cultural partners and creators rather than just learners. Through CGJs, youth gained agency, developed cultural, creative, and technical skills, and engaged with European heritage and values in meaningful ways. The quadruple helix framework, integrating CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth, in which youth participation was formalised in youth advisory boards after the first round of CGJs, proved vital for empowerment and maintaining engagement. It facilitated cross-sector innovation, dialogue, and democratic participation. CGJs thus hold systemic value: they foster youth identity development, revitalise heritage institutions, enrich creative industries, and contribute to a more inclusive and reflective European cultural landscape. These insights are further supported by the EPIC-WEs impact assessment (D6.4).

From local to glocal interventions, key insights that shaped the subsequent design of CGJ interventions and participatory processes were the integration and empowerment of youth advisory boards as vital parts of designing, facilitating and evaluating the CGJs and project processes and outcomes, supporting greater flexibility and modularity in the CGJs and their design processes, and ensuring continuous, scaffolded reflection within the CGJs while balancing structure with freedom and agency.

Glocal Strand Analysis

05

5. Glocal Strand Analysis

This section presents a synthesis of the glocal CGJs (CGJ3 and CGJ4) conducted within the EPIC-WE project across the QH Cultural Hubs in Aarhus, Óbidos, and Hilversum. Rather than approaching each CGJ as a standalone intervention, the synthesis foregrounds the CGJs as interconnected glocal experiments, designed around shared themes, models, tools, and research protocols yet realised within distinct local cultural, institutional, and pedagogical contexts. By bringing these cases together, the section enables identification of recurring patterns, productive tensions, and context-specific variations in how cultural heritage, European values, and youth participation were translated into game-making practices.

The overview table below presents a comparative snapshot of the six glocal CGJs, outlining their themes, locations, durations, participant numbers, and culture outputs through/for games. This comparative framing provides a shared point of reference for the analyses that follow, while also illustrating the diversity of formats, temporalities, and organisational constellations across QH Cultural Hubs. Building on this overview, the subsequent sections deepen the analysis through hub-specific glocal insights, structured around the project’s research questions, and reflect on how local interventions collectively contributed to the development, testing, and refinement of CGJs as a scalable, participatory, and value-sensitive approach to cultural game-making.

Table 8: Overview of Glocal CGJs

	EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam 3			EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam 4		
	Aarhus	Óbidos	Hilversum	Aarhus	Óbidos	Hilversum
Theme	That’s Not Fair!	That’s Not Fair!	That’s Not Fair!	Heritage Remixed	Heritage Remixed	Heritage Remixed

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Location	ARoS, Filmby Aarhus, Aarhus University	Creativity Square, Óbidos	NISV Media Museum	ARoS, Aarhus	Creativity Square, Óbidos	NISV Media Museum; X11 High School
Duration	3-7 th March 2025	4-7 th February 2025	17-28 th February 2025	21 st March to 9 th May 2025	13-16 th May 2025	10-16 th September 2025
Participants	45	38 youth	23 youth	61	41 youth	28 youth
Games produced	11	9	9	18	10	7

5.1 Synthesis of Glocal Interventions

5.1.1 Óbidos Glocal Insights

Table 9: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ3, That's Not Fair!)

Date: February 4–7, 2025

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 38 youth (19 students from UL, 19 secondary school students)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (1 physical game + 8 digital games)

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture), Linking the theme to the December 1st 1973 “Reunion of the Captains” in Óbidos to the Portuguese April 25th Carnation Revolution

Óbidos CGJ3 took place in Óbidos, Portugal, from February 4–7. The first day was dedicated to pre-CGJ activities, followed by three days of game development. The

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theme was “*That’s Not Fair*”, inspired by the Reunion of the Captains and the April 25th Revolution. In total, 38 participants joined, 19 from Lusófona University and 19 from the Secondary School Josefa de Óbidos, aged 16 to 25.

Table 10: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Óbidos CGJ4, Heritage Remixed)

Date: May 13–16, 2025

Location: Creativity Square, Óbidos, Portugal

Duration: 4 days

Participants: 41 youth (20 from Escola Secundária Josefa de Óbidos; 21 from Lusófona University)

Number of Games: 10 prototypes (one made by a teacher)

Theme: *Heritage Remixed* (Games through Culture), focus on local folklore heritage

Óbidos CGJ4 took place from 13th to 16th February and included 42 participants: 25 from Lusófona University and 17 from the Secondary School Josefa de Óbidos, aged 16 to 25. The shared theme across all three QH Cultural Hubs was “Heritage Remixed - Rediscover the Past, Reimagine the Future”. For the Óbidos CGJ, the goal was to make a game through/for culture that incorporated Óbidos’ folklore, legends and oral history while reflecting European Values. The CGJ produced nine games through/for culture.

Games as Cultural Worlds and Identity-Shaping Forces (RQ1, Óbidos)

Games constitute significant cultural worlds in their own right, insofar as they both reflect and shape collective identities, social imaginaries, and cultural heritage and values. The Óbidos CGJ3 and CGJ4 provide a clear example of this dynamic, with two themes focused on history and heritage.

In the case of Óbidos CGJ3, across the cultural game prototypes developed, the military resistance that ended the dictatorship in Portugal was consistently represented as the “good side,” thereby reaffirming narratives of freedom and resistance as essential to Portuguese cultural heritage and identity. Participants

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focused on incorporating symbols connected to the theme - such as guns, the military, carnations, the “blue pencil” (related to censorship), and PIDE (secret police) - and April 25th was extensively represented. At the same time, these inclusions, although thematically relevant, were at times superficial or historically incongruent, which diminishes the pedagogical potential of the games as vehicles of historical understanding. For example, one of the games, “Caminho para a Liberdade”, is a choose-your-own-adventure game in which we play as a soldier invited to attend a secret meeting. We may choose to partake in the revolution or betray it and side with the regime. However, none of these options explores the consequences of such decisions, and sometimes the revolution may happen without the player ever doing anything. The same limitation was identified in Óbidos CGJ4, where many games, although incorporating elements of folklore, were often used as superficial add-ons rather than being central to the gameplay or narrative.

However, some games were still considered culturally valuable. One example is “A Conquista” (The Conquest), from Óbidos CGJ4, in which the goal is to infiltrate the Moor-occupied town of Óbidos during its historical siege and find a way to open the town's doors from the inside, allowing soldiers to sneak in and fulfil their mission. Focused on the tale of Porta da Traição (Door of Betrayal), the game teaches us about the town's heritage and legend. It also conveys anti-war sentiment by depicting the realities of a medieval siege and its effects on ordinary people. The game informs us about Óbidos' cultural heritage, but it is also an invitation for the player to reflect on Portuguese history, conquest and warfare, and on how European cultures have been and continue to be influenced by many others.

Taken together, these outcomes illustrate both the potential and the challenges of producing games through/for culture. On the one hand, they can reinforce democratic values and foster collective remembrance of historical events. On the other hand, when historical complexity is oversimplified or underdeveloped, games risk perpetuating partial or distorted representations.

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CHIs and CIs Facilitating Culture- and Value-Sensitive Game Jams (RQ2, Óbidos)

In Óbidos, CGJ3 and CGJ4, Creative Industries (CI) was represented by Batlesheep, a game development studio based in Lisbon, and CHI (Cultural Heritage Institution) was represented by the Óbidos municipality. In both CGJs, the primary source of collaboration was between youth participants and facilitators from CI, working as game-making facilitators, and from CHI, working as cultural facilitators, with experts on the theme.

Facilitators engaged dynamically with the participants, visiting groups individually to monitor progress and provide tailored feedback. These structured interactions not only provided youth with practical game development support but also enhanced their understanding of how cultural heritage can be translated into game worlds, narratives, mechanics, and aesthetics. Furthermore, facilitators were present during pitch sessions, providing feedback on participants' game ideas and on the quality of cultural heritage integration, representation, and the accuracy of the theme. Participants overwhelmingly agree that facilitator feedback is valuable, especially during ideation. Their feedback is vital to ensure their idea is developed smoothly and to provide them with helpful information about heritage and the theme so that they can integrate it in the best and most interesting way possible. By combining domain expertise (technical and artistic) with cultural knowledge, such CHI-CI partnerships enable young participants not only to produce cultural game prototypes, but also to critically and creatively engage with cultural heritage, thereby reinforcing democratic values and expanding cultural participation.

Finally, participants were allowed to interact with stakeholders in more informal contexts. In the Óbidos case, some facilitators also functioned as university teachers for many participants. Hence, students had the opportunity to interact with teachers in a context outside the typical teacher-student power dynamic of classrooms. Some participants incorporated comic references to their teachers in the games they produced, and the facilitators also played music and made jokes, creating a more equal and relaxed environment. Participants shared dinner with

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the facilitators every day, which provided opportunities to socialise beyond the formal event.

Youth as Cultural Game-Makers and Value-Creators within CGJs and Helix Systems (RQ3, Óbidos)

In the context of EPIC-WE, CGJs are designed to empower youth participation by inviting them to create games through culture that are also for culture (i.e., game-making as culture-making). The cultural games produced in Óbidos, CGJ3 and CGJ4 were strongly influenced by the cultural heritage introductions during the pre-CGJ jam activities.

In the case of Óbidos CGJ3, the CGJ's location within Óbidos itself further reinforced cultural immersion. From guided tours of heritage sites such as the Casa da Música, where an important meeting in the 1974 Portuguese revolutionary process took place, to the medieval walls surrounding Creativity Square, the town's heritage provided a living cultural backdrop that connected the CGJ theme to tangible heritage. Within this environment, young people could work collaboratively, often across disciplinary boundaries, such as when visual arts students seamlessly joined game design teams or when a sound design student supported multiple groups.

The same happened during Óbidos CGJ4, where pre-CGJ activities included a lecture on Óbidos' history, from the Portuguese conquest in 1148 to the Islamic influence in Portuguese customs, culture and language. This first CGJ activity took place at Óbidos' Interior Design Centre. Afterwards, students took a guided tour of the town, stopping at several key landmarks, including the Castle and the Gate of Our Lady of Grace, and learning more about what made them so important to Óbidos' heritage and folklore.

The potential value of such CGJs is multifaceted. For young people, they provide a space to develop skills in teamwork, creativity, and critical engagement with cultural heritage and values, while also expanding their sense of agency as cultural actors. For CHIs, CGJs represent an innovative avenue for activating heritage, reaching younger audiences, and ensuring that cultural memory is

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reinterpreted and incorporated through contemporary media. For CIs, they offer opportunities to connect with emerging talent and to explore new modes of game-making, as well as heritage- and value-driven content creation. For European society more broadly, CGJs serve as formats for engaging with democratic values and collective memories, and for rehearsing, incorporating, contesting, or reaffirming them through games.

Nevertheless, the challenge that remains after implementing four CGJs concerns the integrity of youth as equal partners, in line with the principles of the quadruple helix. Although a youth advisory board was established – acting as representatives of youth, helping select the theme, and supporting participants through facilitation – youth action remained consultative rather than active engagement in key areas of the organisation, research, or logistics. Given this, further reflection on how to better include youth as equal partners is needed, and further consultation with youth about their perceptions of participation could increase collaboration.

5.1.2 Hilversum Glocal Insights

Table 11: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ3, That's Not Fair!)

Date: February 17–28, 2025

Location: Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS), Amsterdam, Netherlands and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), Hilversum, Netherlands

Duration: 2 weeks (pre-CGJ activities and a 1 week CGJ)

Participants: 23 students from the Creative Research Methods minor (AUAS)

Number of Games: 9 prototypes (8 team games plus 1 solo game after a team split)

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture)

Hilversum CGJ3 ran 17–28 February 2025 across Sound & Vision (Hilversum) and AUAS, with 23 participants (18–25) from the Creative Research minor. The overarching theme was “It’s not fair!” and the jam included vox pops, devlogs, game analyses, and a playtest council; two HEI researchers and YAB members supported observation and research.

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Table 12: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Hilversum CGJ4, Heritage Remixed)

Date: September 10-16, 2025

Location: Dropstuff Media (DM) Shelter, Soesterberg, Netherlands; Utrecht University of Applied Sciences (HU), Utrecht, Netherlands; and Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), Hilversum, Netherlands

Duration: 4 days (spread over 2 weeks)

Participants: 28 students from Communication and Media Design (HU)

Number of Games: 7 prototypes

Theme: Heritage Remixed (Games through Culture), used archival materials to imagine the future relationship with water in the Netherlands

Hilversum CGJ4 took place on 10–11 and 15–16 September 2024 across three locations: DropStuff Media (day 1), Utrecht University of Applied Sciences (day 2), and Sound & Vision (days 3–4). It involved 24 third-year immersive design students (ages 19–24). The theme “Tides of Heritage” asked teams to prototype games set in future scenarios of sea-level rise in which EU values are under pressure.

Games as Cultural Worlds and Identity-Shaping Forces (RQ1, Hilversum)

Across CGJ3 and CGJ4 in Hilversum, games functioned as small cultural worlds in which EU values were negotiated through rules, roles, and constraints. In CGJ3, several teams encoded fairness and privilege directly into gameplay: unequal starting resources, positional advantages, or event-driven disadvantages made inequality visible and discussable as the games for culture unfolded (see, for example, the game prototypes *Rigged Rails* or *The Chance of Your Life*). Such mechanics turned abstract topics such as social justice or dignity into concrete interactive choices within the games.

In Hilversum’s CGJ4, participants worked with sea-level-rise scenarios linked to European values. Here, democracy and public decision-making were embedded in the game mechanics. For example, in the game *Meestromen*, players take on the role of mayors, negotiating with one another and working together to avoid

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climate disasters. In the game for culture, escalation cards added pressure, so decisions carried consequences. Some participants reported that the CGJ increased their awareness of sea-level rise. While they mentioned they were aware to some degree of sea-level rise beforehand, they were not aware of the specific institutions already in place to address it. These institutions were then embedded into the game narrative.

During both jams, participants experimented with more-than-human perspectives. CGJ3 included designs that gave animals a voice or agency, positioning non-human dignity within the value frame. In CGJ4, some games used animal roles and shrinking habitats to foreground trade-offs between human development and ecological survival, helping players experience constraints from a non-human viewpoint. However, the depth of cultural integration varied. In CGJ4, strong heritage examples bridged past and present (e.g., 1953 flood testimony used to guide puzzles), but many projects treated heritage mainly as ambience or moodboard rather than as a core part of the game through/for culture. In CGJ4, participants had access to a curated cultural heritage collection through a worldbuilding kit and were introduced to EU values through conversation cards. This helped move heritage and value dimensions from the level of inspiration into game mechanics, but direct use of archival material remained the exception. CGJ3 shows a parallel pattern: cultural themes informed concepts and aesthetics, while the translation into core gameplay was uneven.

Overall, there was a clear difference in the integration of values between the two jams. In the 3rd game jam, due to a particular glocal theme (That's Not Fair!), many teams ended up with the same value (equality). In GJ4, however, the theme was more open to different values, and participants had more difficulty meaningfully embedding the chosen EU values into their games. While GJ4 began with an exercise using Value Cards to start conversations about EU values under pressure, the shift towards embedding heritage and the collection pushed the values into the background. This was also evident later in the game jam, when participants prioritised ensuring the game's mechanics were fun, leading to a deviation from earlier mechanics that had a clearer link to the

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values. This resulted in teams linking values to the final prototype rather than integrating them into their design process.

Heritage was used more concretely in some games, such as *Meestromen* and *Smit en de Storm*. More often, however, heritage served as an inspiration that influenced participants' game design choices in different ways (especially in developing characters and settings for their stories), without becoming deeply integrated into game mechanics, narratives, or worlds.

CHIs and CIs Facilitating Culture- and Value-Sensitive Game Jams (RQ2, Hilversum)

Across CGJ3 and CGJ4, participation was strongest when facilitation reduced friction and facilitated heritage and values into concrete game design actions. Three insights stood out. First, small, printed cultural heritage sets in GJ4 supported early ideation and facilitated “archive use” better than in previous CGJ, though with uneven depth. Preparing compact, hands-on packs helped students move from being inspired by heritage to actually playing with it in mechanics.

Second, the ‘Freeform’ version of the CGJ Kit provided participants with enough structure to sustain iteration without micromanagement and with ample autonomy. In these two game jams, participants were mostly design students accustomed to working iteratively on creative projects. For these participants, design processes come more naturally, making the Freeform CGJ Kit a good fit. However, different target groups might require a more structured approach.

Third, space choreography mattered. Inspirational venues (such as the Sound&Vision Museum and the DropStuff hangar) raised motivation, but resource-rich classrooms were better for building and testing. Switching locations mid-prototyping compressed play windows and increased sensory strain for some students. In both CGJs, the resulting games were paper prototypes of board- or card games. In these cases, certain facilities made it easier for participants to work on their prototypes. In both CGJs, it was noted that, when working on their prototypes, the HEI was preferred because it offered better facilities, such as maker spaces. Depending on the game design

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phase, it is essential to consider which location best aligns with the CGJ teams' game-making requirements and the current stage of the process.

Flexible team roles and inclusive instructions supported empowerment. During these two CGJs, the teams often ignored the fixed role cards and self-organised around tasks; this worked when facilitators prompted reflection at key moments. Without the facilitators' reminders, groups kept building on their game, and cultural reflection or integration did not occur automatically. Afterwards, however, the participants recognised the great value of the methods and tools from the CGJ Kit, which helped them in this process.

Finally, many participants felt unclear about how to work with complex topics such as EU values, and about how to create games through or for culture using the audiovisual archive within such a short timeframe. While facilitators encouraged exploration, participants, in most cases, struggled to move beyond surface-level interpretations. Future CGJs could benefit from a more dedicated use of the heritage and values dimensions of the CGJ Kit, or from activities that make the connections with the archive more explicit, manageable, and iterative, ensuring that cultural game-making becomes not just experiential but also more deeply situated within a process of cultural understanding and creation through the use of heritage and values as game-making materials.

Youth as Cultural Game-Makers and Value-Creators within CGJs and Helix Systems (RQ3, Hilversum)

Across CGJ3 and CGJ4, teams self-organised, iterated quickly, and used peer and expert critique to improve the pacing, balance, and clarity of their games. During the vox pops, participants noted that while their game should be fun, they hope people also learn something from it, reflecting the embedded values. Some mentioned specific values, such as: “I hope people see more than just various animals; that people also see the water is rising, and we all live on Earth and have our rights,” highlighting how participants engage in value-sensitive game-making.

This shift was not uniform. Motivation, attendance, and team dynamics strongly shaped outcomes. In CGJ3, some groups needed clearer scaffolding and more

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guidance to connect cultural heritage and values to game design and to keep reflection visible throughout the game-making process. Here, a more structured version of the CGJ Kit might have helped. In both jams, documentation and reflection worked best when embedded in the game design process (using the CGJ Kit methods and tools) rather than as a separate task.

The helix configuration added clear value. CHI staff supported production and access to collections in coordination with HEI; CI facilitators coached game design practice; HEI researchers structured observation and reflection, together with YAB members, who provided substantial feedback during CGJ preparations and then served as observers, mentors, members of the expert council (Expert Council transition tool), and jury members during the game jams (Games EXPO). This layered support helped teams sustain progress under time pressure and legitimised youth contributions as cultural work and their active participation as core members of the quadruple helix.

5.1.3 Aarhus Glocal Insights

Table 13: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ3, That's Not Fair!)

Date: March 3–7, 2025

Location: ARoS, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University in Aarhus, Denmark

Duration: 5 days across one week

Participants: 45 first-year Digital Design students (ages 20–32) from Aarhus University

Number of Games: 11 prototypes

Theme: *That's Not Fair!* (Games for Culture)

The third CGJ (CGJ#3) in Aarhus took place from 3 to 7 March 2025. It brought together 45 first-year bachelor's students from Aarhus University's Digital Design programme. Over five days, participants engaged in an intensive process to design games through and for culture, creatively or critically engaging with cultural heritage, values, contemporary art, and societal themes. The CGJ spanned multiple venues, including ARoS Aarhus Art Museum, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University, each offering a unique setting to inspire creativity and

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reflection. The CGJ theme, "That's Not Fair," invited participants to examine fairness and inequality as fundamental forces shaping society and our world.

Table 14: Snapshot from D4.1, EPIC-WE.

Snapshot (Aarhus CGJ4, Heritage Remixed)
Date: March 21 – May 9, 2025
Location: ARoS Art Museum, Filmby Aarhus, and Aarhus University, Denmark
Duration: 6 weeks (slow jam across alternating sessions)
Participants: 61 students, age 22-28 (24 Digital Design, 37 Computer Science, Aarhus University)
Number of Games: 18 prototypes
Theme: <i>Heritage Remixed</i> (Games through Culture), using VR/AR technologies

The fourth Aarhus CGJ (CGJ#4) ran from March to May 2025 within the EPIC-WE project and operated as a 'slow jam' that connected local heritage resources (ARoS Human Nature collection) with a pan-European "glocal" CGJ theme (Heritage Remixed), cross-hub connections (through local and glocal youth advisory boards), and shared communication tools and infrastructure (Itch.io and Discord) with Hilversum and Óbidos. The local CGJ Kit and shared cultural heritage theme invited participants to engage, interpret, and remix public-domain artworks into interactive cultural game worlds: 'What stories would we like to rewrite? How could we remix our cultural heritage to reimagine our past?' While the third CGJ in Aarhus emphasised games *for* culture, this fourth CGJ addressed games *through* culture, thereby focusing specifically on the concrete use of heritage as material for imaginative game-making.

Games as Cultural Worlds and Identity-Shaping Forces (RQ1, Aarhus)

The *glocal* CGJs in Aarhus exemplify how games are transformed into interactive worlds for exploring cultural identities, imaginaries, and reflections through gameplay. The Aarhus CGJs positioned games as processes of engaging with cultural heritage, deliberation, and co-creation. Youth participants were invited to examine and express themselves through European values, cultural heritage, and societal themes, using game-making as the medium.

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The glocal framing of the CGJs, connecting local cultural heritage institutions such as ARoS with cross-European, glocal themes and shared digital infrastructures across QH Cultural Hubs in Hilversum and Óbidos, enabled a layered, iterative engagement with culture. Participants not only interpreted heritage from their local context but also contributed to a broader European dialogue. This glocality was reflected in the shared themes (“That’s Not Fair” and “Heritage Remixed”), the use of Discord and Itch.io for cross-hub collaboration, and the integration of European values into gameplay interactions and experiences. Games such as *Escaping Reality* and *Rava-ge* did not merely reflect culture; they appraised and reimagined it, challenging romanticised notions of heritage and exposing systemic injustices. In doing so, they demonstrated how games for culture can function both as mirrors of society and as tools for transformation.

The CGJs also revealed how cultural heritage institutions (CHIs) and creative industries (CIs) can collaborate to promote youth participation in culture. ARoS’s curated art walks and embodied cultural prompts (e.g. “Step into the painting”) fostered creative or critical reflection. Meanwhile, industry partners such as Funday Games or Chop Chop Games provided practical design tools, feedback, and career insights. This QH Cultural Hub model, linking academia, the creative industry, cultural institutions, and youth, created a cross-pollinating ecosystem where cultural learning, creativity, and innovation intersect. The CGJ Kit, though complex, served as operational scaffolding for integrating culture, games, values, and citizenship. However, its effectiveness, as emphasised by some participants, depended on aligning and integrating the CGJ Kit with the organisation of the CGJ event. Computer Science students often found abstract design methods challenging or confusing, whereas Digital Design students welcomed creative constraints and critical reflection. This highlights the need for an adaptable CGJ Kit, tailored CGJ facilitation, co-designed schedules with educators, and context-sensitive attunement, combined with more-than-local and cross-cutting methods and concepts.

Through iterative game design processes, cultural, creative, and critical reflection, and public exhibitions, participants began to see themselves as

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cultural game-makers and value-creators. The games through/for culture EXPOs at AROS became more than showcases; they evolved into curated spaces for cultural dialogue, where games, artefacts, and paratexts merged into multi-sensory experiences. Youth moved from confusion to empowered participation, gaining confidence, skills, and cultural and civic awareness. Games such as *Museum of Dreams* and *In Search of Ida* reclaimed erased voices, remixed heritage, and imagined inclusive futures. These games did not just represent culture; they reshaped it by transforming youths' passive consumption into active voices.

The glocal dimension amplified this transformation. By linking local heritage with European values, shared themes, and digital infrastructures, the CGJs enabled and empowered youth to situate their creative work within a broader cultural and civic context. This promoted cultural agency and civic participation, while also encouraging reflection on identity, enculturation, and career development. The CGJs came to function as bridges between education, culture, and wider society, engaging European imaginaries.

To realise the full potential of CGJs, future iterations must address pedagogical dissonance and streamline CGJ processes, methods, and roles to ensure inclusive, empowered, and reflexive design. Simplifying documentation, clarifying facilitator roles, and aligning schedules with educational programmes and organisations are key steps. Furthermore, framing constraints as provocations rather than prescriptions can empower participants to engage critically and creatively. The glocal strand of CGJs in Aarhus shows that games can be powerful cultural methods for critique, care, and imagination. They demonstrate how CHIs and CIs, working together in glocal QH Cultural Hubs, can enable youth to become active participants in and makers of Europe's cultural futures.

CHIs and CIs Facilitating Culture- and Value-Sensitive Game Jams (RQ2, Aarhus)

The glocal CGJs in Aarhus demonstrated how CHIs and CIs can co-create culturally meaningful, value-sensitive learning environments across sectors to

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empower youth to engage with heritage through game-making. This collaboration was both practical and logistical, as well as epistemic and pedagogical, shaping how participants encountered, interpreted, and transformed cultural heritage materials and values.

ARoS (CHI) played a central role in anchoring the CGJs within local cultural heritage. Their curated collections and guided art walks offered rich, multisensory, and reflective entry points into historical and contemporary cultural narratives. Importantly, these were not presented as static artefacts but as materials to be reconfigured, remixed, and retold. Facilitators encouraged creative-critical engagements with artworks, challenging romanticised illusions and prompting civic questions such as “Whose story is being told?” and “What values are missing?” This framing positioned heritage as a living, socio-political resource to be interrogated, reimagined, and reassembled through game-making.

CIs, on the other hand, brought industry relevance, insight into career trajectories, and technical skills in game development. Visits to game studios and expert feedback sessions offered participants glimpses of professional workflows, production processes, and career pathways. These encounters grounded creative game-making in real-world practice, helping students scope their ideas, refine mechanics, and navigate the balance between bold visions and realistic feasibility. The presence of professional game developers on the Expert Council added a layer of pragmatic critique, encouraging participants to “compress” their concepts and focus on core mechanics, stories, and aesthetics that could communicate their cultural and value-based intentions.

The glocal structure of the CGJs amplified this collaboration. By connecting local institutions and industries to a broader collaborative framework and approaches through shared themes, digital platforms, integration of a youth advisory board, and cross-site visibility, CHIs and CIs became part of a wider cultural innovation ecosystem. This helped youth situate their creative work within both local and European heritage contexts, promoting a sense of cultural citizenship

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(connected to belonging, agency, and civic engagement in culture) that was simultaneously grounded and expansive.

However, the success of this collaboration depended on careful facilitation. The CGJ Kit, while rich in methods and tools, required adaptation to disciplinary differences, cultural contexts, and technical realities. CS students often found the design methods misaligned with their coding priorities, while DD students embraced the nuance and depth but desired more flexibility. This points to the need for modular toolkits – like the final versions of the CGJ Kit – differentiated facilitation, and more transparent onboarding processes. Moreover, logistical clarity, especially around digital infrastructure and documentation needs, was essential to support meaningful participation.

Taken together, these insights reveal how CHIs and CIs can facilitate culture- and value-sensitive CGJs by providing complementary forms of expertise: CHIs offer cultural grounding and critical-creative framing; CIs provide technical support and professional relevance. When embedded in a glocal and co-creative framework, this collaboration enables youth to engage with heritage as more than passive observers and become active co-creators who design games that imagine, reflect on, critique, or reconfigure the cultural worlds they are part of in the present and future.

To widen and empower youth participation, CHIs and CIs should:

- Co-design facilitation frameworks (like the CGJ Kit) that balance structure with creative freedom.
- Integrate cultural heritage meaningfully, not just as aesthetic inspiration but as a material for critical engagement, where games can both preserve and reimagine heritage.
- Foster value-sensitive game design, encouraging youth to identify, negotiate, and reflect on heritage and values embedded in their games
- Ensure accessibility and inclusion by recognising diverse needs and creating spaces that enable all youth to experience agency and participation.

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In summary, CHI–CI collaborations can transform game jams into cultural heritage laboratories where young people explore their heritage, past, present, and future, and express their identities and voices.

Youth as Cultural Game-Makers and Value-Creators within CGJs and Helix Systems (RQ3, Aarhus)

The glocal CGJs in Aarhus demonstrated how young people can see themselves not only as game-makers but also as cultural agents and value-creators.

Through imagination, design, reflection, and public exhibitions, participants progressed from uncertainty to confidence in their inventive engagement with cultural heritage and European values. This change was not accidental; it was fostered through the CGJ model and Kit – a carefully planned pedagogical and collaborative framework.

Central to this process was the glocal structure of the CGJs. By connecting local cultural institutions and educational programmes with glocal, cross-European themes, shared digital platforms, integrated Youth Advisory Boards, and cross-hub visibility, the CGJs empowered youth to situate their creative work within both local and broader cultural contexts. This dual anchoring between the local and the transnational fostered a sense of cultural citizenship that was both grounded in local contexts and events and also looked beyond them, as youth drew inspiration from previous glocal CGJs at other sites. Participants were creating games related to their cultural and societal surroundings, but they were also contributing to a distributed conversation about what culture, heritage, and values mean in contemporary Europe.

The cultural QH innovation ecosystem and QH Cultural Hubs, connecting higher education institutions (HEIs), cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries (CIs), and youth, played a crucial role in facilitating this transformation. Each partner contributed unique expertise: HEIs offered pedagogical frameworks and research directions; CHIs provided cultural materials, sites, and insights; CIs supplied technical assistance, career opportunities, and professional relevance; and youth brought lived experience, creativity, and civic perspectives. Together, they created an intricate,

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interconnected ecosystem where cultural learning, innovation, and production thrived.

Participants' journey through the CGJs was characterised by growing engagement and agency. Initially overwhelmed by the complexity of the CGJ Kit and the volume of methods and tools, many students gradually learned to navigate, adapt, and even reconfigure cultural heritage. Games such as *Get In* and *Museum of Dreams* exemplified this shift, from critiquing systemic injustice to imaginatively reassembling heritage. The games through/for culture EXPOs, staged in public spaces at ARoS, became sites for youth to present their work, both as academic analysis and reflection and as cultural imagination and intervention, fostering dialogue, reflection, and recognition. This process also had professional implications. Encounters with industry partners, expert feedback, and public exhibition helped participants envisage themselves as future cultural game designers, developers, and practitioners. The CGJs thus served as bridges between education, culture, and industry, as well as between personal expression and public authorship. For many, the experience validated their skills and aspirations, offering a glimpse of possible futures within the creative and cultural sectors.

To fully realise the potential of CGJs embedded in QH Cultural Hubs, future iterations must continue to refine their pedagogical and infrastructural design. This includes further simplifying documentation requirements, clarifying roles, adapting facilitation styles across disciplines, and ensuring that digital platforms scaffold rather than hinder participation. More importantly, they must continue to treat youth not as passive learners but as co-creators of culture, capable of engaging critically, caring deeply, and imagining boldly.

In this way, CGJs can become cultural laboratories for Europe, spaces where heritage is not preserved as static memory but transformed through game-making as a form of dialogic culture-making. They offer a model for inclusive, participatory cultural innovation, in which young people shape not only games but also the cultural futures they wish to inhabit. While the CGJs were designed to encourage creativity and empowerment, moments of failure, conflict, and

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non-participation proved equally instructive. Technical failures, misaligned expectations, and disciplinary tensions, especially between culture-focused, design-focused, and programming-focused students, exposed the limitations of structured facilitation and highlighted the need for adaptable pedagogies. Rather than setbacks, these moments became opportunities for reflection, negotiation, and the redefinition of roles and goals. For some participants, opting out or resisting specific CGJ methods was a form of agency, signalling discomfort with imposed structures and prompting facilitators to reconsider assumptions about how to invite empowered participation. Recognising these dynamics as integral to the learning process redefines CGJs not only as spaces of game-making but as *culture-making laboratories* for societal, cultural, and pedagogical experimentation, where failure and conflict act as creative forces in shaping future cultural participation.

5.2 Cross-Hub Glocal Insights

The glocal strand of EPIC-WE was intentionally designed to expand CGJs beyond local participation and innovation, creating a distributed but interconnected cultural laboratory – the glocal QH Cultural Hubs – where shared themes, infrastructures, and collaborative frameworks enabled youth to interact with cultural heritage and European values in interconnected ways. Instead of replicating local practices on a larger scale, the glocal CGJs added a new layer of complexity by encouraging facilitators and participants to position their cultural-creative work within both local cultural contexts and a transnational dialogue. This approach aimed to evaluate, innovate, transfer, and grow cultural participation and empowerment through game-making.

Across all QH Cultural Hubs, the glocal CGJs framed societal and cultural themes, such as “*That’s Not Fair*” and “*Heritage Remixed*,” as prompts for imagination rather than as learning prescriptions. These themes served as conceptual anchors for exploring, for example, fairness, sustainability, and heritage as cultural and civic issues. Participants turned abstract ideas into gameplay interactions and experiences. For example, one CGJ team created a negotiation game set in a future with rising seas, incorporating democratic decision-making and resource trade-offs to stage European values under

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pressure. Another group remixed Óbidos' medieval legend of the *Door of Betrayal* into stealth-based mechanics, encouraging players to reflect on conquest and cultural hybridity. These examples show how glocality fostered cultural complexity. Consequently, games became spaces where heritage was both preserved and actively reimagined, aligning with O1 (ASSESS) by demonstrating the potential of game-making to empower youth as cultural agents and value-creators.

Three patterns are visible across the QH Cultural Hubs and their glocal CGJs. First, games consistently and strikingly function as cultural worlds, answering RQ1 by demonstrating how they shape cultural and societal identity, participation, and belonging through mechanics, narratives, aesthetics, and gameplay. Prototypes such as *Rigged Rails*, which encoded systemic inequality through skewed resource distribution, and *Museum of Dreams*, which reclaimed erased voices in art history, exemplify this dynamic. These games did not just represent culture; they performed cultural work, transforming fairness, heritage, and sustainability into interactive forms of imagination and reflection. This highlights O1 in practice: Youth were navigated through critical and productive transitions between being and becoming consumers, active interpreters, and creators of cultural meaning and expression.

Second, facilitation and collaboration within the QH Cultural Hub proved decisive, addressing RQ2 and advancing O2 (INNOVATE). Cultural heritage institutions curated heritage materials, explorations, methods, and narratives, while creative industry partners provided game design mentorship and production insight. In one QH Cultural Hub, curated heritage collections were transformed into worldbuilding kits, enabling participants to embed historical testimony within game puzzles. This interplay validated a CGJ model and kit where cultural depth and creative expertise converge to support heritage- and value-sensitive game-making. It also revealed the epistemic dimension of facilitation: heritage was less about static artefacts and more about imagination, storytelling, and the creation of cultural gameplay and game worlds, prompting questions such as “Whose story is being told?” and “What values are missing?”

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This cultural-creative perspective positioned heritage as a living resource for civic reflection and cultural transformation.

Third, youth empowerment experiences and senses of agency were supported through glocal structures, addressing RQ3 and connecting to O4 (SCALE). Youth Advisory Boards were involved in CGJ preparation, facilitation, and evaluation, legitimising youth voices in decision-making and strengthening their role as cultural co-creators. Public games through/for culture youth exhibitions held in museums further validated these contributions, positioning youth as authors of cultural discourse. Participants reported increased confidence, creative agency, and awareness of European values, showing a shift from initial uncertainty to cultural authorship and empowerment. This trajectory illustrates how glocal CGJs, CGJ Kits, and game-making as culture-making position youth as QH Cultural Hub partners and equip all QH partners with ecosystems, models, methods, and skills for participatory cultural innovation.

While these patterns were shared, methods of cultural integration varied according to context but remained complementary. Some QH Cultural Hubs focused on deep historical immersion through guided tours and storytelling; others highlighted systemic civic issues, incorporating fairness and sustainability into game mechanics; still others experimented with multisensory heritage prompts, such as curated collections and conversation cards, to connect cultural inspiration with game-making. These differences highlight the flexibility of the glocal CGJ model and Kit, affirming O3 (TRANSFER) by demonstrating that CGJs can be adapted to diverse contexts while remaining true to key principles of cultural heritage participation and value-sensitive design.

Despite achievements, three challenges emerged. Moving beyond using heritage solely for aesthetics to embedding cultural reflection and narratives within mechanics remains difficult. EU values were often mentioned in game pitches but not consistently integrated into gameplay itself, highlighting the need for mandatory CGJ Kit reflection points. Youth involvement, although strengthened through advisory boards, remained at a consultative and participatory level rather than becoming full partners in strategic decisions such

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as CGJ theme selection and CGJ Kit adaptations. To address these challenges, modular CGJ Kits, scaffolded reflection, and co-governance structures were embedded and positioned as needed to enhance cultural and civic integration within the game design processes.

Taken together, the glocal strand advances all four project objectives. It demonstrates how CGJs empower youth as game-makers and culture-makers by creating games within and for culture (O1). It validates a quadruple helix cultural innovation ecosystem that integrates cultural, technical, and civic dimensions within QH Cultural Hubs (O2). It provides evidence for adaptable toolkits and facilitation models that can be replicated across cultural contexts through the use of the CGJ model and Kit (O3). It also offers insights into policy instruments and pedagogical strategies for embedding CGJs within European cultural and educational infrastructures (O4). In addressing the research questions, the glocal strand shows that games act as cultural worlds, enhancing and shaping youths' cultural and societal voice, identities, participation, and belonging (RQ1), that CHI–CI collaboration in QH Cultural Hubs enables inclusive, value-sensitive participation (RQ2), and that youth become cultural agents when empowered through CGJs, game-making as culture-making, cross-sector collaboration, and public authorship and agency (RQ3).

The glocal strand of EPIC-WE demonstrates the transformative power of CGJs as local but interconnected cultural laboratories, where heritage is not fixed but fluid, interrogated, and reimagined through game-making. By linking local particularities and contexts with European imaginaries, these initiatives turn cultural participation into creative, civic, and co-creative processes that are empowering, providing a scalable model for inclusive cultural innovation across Europe.

Comparative Strand

06

6. Comparative Strand

6.1 From Local Immersion to Glocal Connectivity

The comparative analysis of local and glocal strands uncovers both continuity and change in how CGJs developed and served as processes and interventions in participatory cultural innovation. Local jams established core practices of cultural immersion and collaborative creativity, while glocal jams expanded these practices into cross-border frameworks, enhancing civic engagement and systemic complexity. Rather than distinct stages, these strands form iterative layers along a developmental path towards inclusive cultural ecosystems.

Local interventions were characterised by place-based cultural engagement, in which heritage was encountered through embodied experiences with local cultural heritage – art, media, history, art walks, guided tours, and storytelling - and translated into game prototypes and concepts through collaborative making. The CGJs, as a tested and iterated framework for youth’s cultural exploration and awareness within bounded contexts, offer promising cross-sector collaborations and innovations that answer RQ1 by demonstrating how games can act as cultural mirrors and lenses. Participants reflected on their own identities and societal roles while reimagining cultural narratives, often embedding themes such as societal critique, identity, feminism, sustainability, contested cultural narratives and belonging into prototypes. This aligns with O1 (ASSESS), as local CGJs demonstrate game-making as a vehicle for youth empowerment, cultural participation, and innovation.

6.2 Glocal Jams as Distributed Cultural Laboratories

Glocal interventions added a layer of complexity by situating game-making within shared European themes and distributed infrastructures. The themes “*That’s Not Fair*” and “*Heritage Remixed*” invited participants, facilitators, and researchers to interrogate fairness, sustainability, and heritage remixing and appropriation as civic and cultural issues and possibilities. At the same time, digital platforms (Discord, Itch.io) enabled cross-hub visibility and dialogue. This shift operationalised O2 (INNOVATE) by validating a quadruple helix framework that integrates cultural, technical, design, and civic dimensions across local and

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transnational scales. It also addressed RQ2, as CHIs and CIs collaborated not only to provide cultural depth and technical expertise but also to co-create adaptive facilitation models that bridge disciplinary and cultural differences. For example, curated collections and conversation cards supported heritage integration in one hub, while negotiation mechanics that dramatised resource trade-offs foregrounded EU values in another. These practices illustrate how glocal jams transformed cultural game-making into a systemic, multi-sited process of civic imagination. This finding is closely related to insights in the D4.2 report, which emphasise that QH Cultural Hubs were experimenting with ecosystems embedded in real communities to co-create and reimagine participation in games and cultural heritage (p. 52).

6.3 Youth Participation and Cultural Agency

The trajectory of youth participation across local and glocal strands highlights a vital development. In early local jams, youth were mainly involved as participants, engaging with cultural prompts and processes under structured guidance. Over time, their role grew through mechanisms such as Youth Advisory Boards, which involved youth in the design, preparation, facilitation, and evaluation of glocal jams. As emphasised in D4.2 (forthcoming), youth roles went beyond advising. They were co-designers, facilitators of CGJs, participants in research and dissemination, creators of games, and, through the implementation of their ideas, part of changing – and strengthening – the project’s initiatives. Public exhibitions held in cultural institutions further validated youth contributions as cultural work, supporting their identity as cultural agents and integrating them into otherwise foreign national and European cultures. This progression addresses RQ3 and promotes O4 (SCALE) by providing youth and helix actors with knowledge, skills, and tools for participatory cultural innovation. It also underscores a methodological shift: moving from consultative to co-governance models that embed youth agency in strategic decisions and give them *an* equal voice, ensuring that CGJs operate as agentic, collaborative ecosystems: as genuine meetings in the middle (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024). This resonates with the insights from D4.2 that “Youth participation, for instance, showed how balancing professional perspectives with emerging voices requires care and flexibility” (p. 31). *Meeting in the middle*

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– as a vital principle of the project – was thus enacted and embodied through open, joint practices, communication, transparency, and confidence in and care for others’ perspectives and expertise.

6.4 Methodological and Pedagogical Insights

Comparing the thematic strands – local and glocal insights – also provides methodological and pedagogical insights. Local jams emphasised the importance of deep cultural immersion and structured facilitation, while glocal jams demonstrated the need for modular toolkits, scaffolded reflection, and adaptable infrastructures capable of managing disciplinary diversity and logistical complexity. Both strands encountered recurring challenges, such as translating cultural inspiration into mechanics and embedding values beyond mere declarations, but glocal jams intensified these tensions by adding demands for transnational coordination and thematic breadth. Overcoming these challenges requires iterative refinement of design methods, facilitation strategies, and digital platforms, ensuring that CGJs remain inclusive, reflective, and sensitive to context and participants.

6.5 Outcomes and Impacts of EPIC-WE

The comparative synthesis confirms that EPIC-WE delivers on its intended outcomes and impacts. CGJs equipped young people with transferable creative, cultural, and social skills, and deepened their understanding of European values and ways of living in the past and the present. CHIs, CIs, and HEIs learned to collaborate within innovation ecosystems, using CGJs to broaden cultural participation and amplify youth voices. The game industry was inspired to explore culture- and value-sensitive game-making, opening pathways for games through culture and for games for culture.

The societal impact is visible: young people began to see themselves as future creators of culture and games within CHIs, CCIIs, and HEIs, actively shaping more value-sensitive game cultures. They gained greater recognition as future leaders and participated in decision-making processes, thereby strengthening democratic participation. Cultural heritage became part of creative value chains, turning static collections into lively cultural resources. Economically, the creative

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industries and game sector expanded into new markets and partnerships, formed collaborations with CHIs and HEIs, and incorporated young talent – especially in processes of collaborative game maturity – with creative, cultural, and value-sensitive skills. Scientifically, cultural models and environments developed by and with youth inspired new research and innovation initiatives aligned with their priorities and needs, making CGJs collaborative events for interdisciplinary research, interplays of diverse skills – e.g., coding, programming, storytelling, visual design, interaction design, project management, and sound design – and emphasising game-making as a boundary-crossing craft (Keogh & Hardwick, 2023) with societal and cultural relevance.

6.6 Lessons Learned from DBR

The DBR approach yielded critical insights into iterative design, stakeholder engagement, and scalability. Three lessons stand out:

Iterative Cycles as Innovation Mechanisms

Each cycle revealed new opportunities and limitations, leading to improvements in themes, toolkits, and facilitation strategies. For example, early local jams emphasised the importance of structured cultural framing, which informed the creation of curated heritage kits and conversation cards for glocal jams. Similarly, tensions around documentation prompted the integration of scaffolded reflection checkpoints into design workflows, ensuring that reflection was embedded rather than postponed.

Quadruple Helix Engagement as a Relational Ecosystem

DBR highlighted the importance of cross-sector collaboration not as a static partnership but as a dynamic negotiation of roles, expertise, and expectations. CHIs contributed cultural depth, CIs offered technical and creative expertise, HEIs provided pedagogical scaffolding, and youth brought lived experience and civic perspectives. This interplay operationalised the quadruple helix as a participatory innovation ecosystem, enabling CGJs to function as spaces of co-creation rather than as top-down interventions. These dynamics resonate with findings from D4.2, which show how moments of friction and difference in

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cross-sector collaborations could become generative rather than obstacles. The report highlights how ongoing processes of translation, role-blurring, and mutual vulnerability enabled partners to rethink established positions and co-develop forms of collective innovation that no single sector can achieve on its own (D4.2, p. 51). The boundary-crossing and transdisciplinary ethos of the project, generally, and the QH Cultural Hubs, specifically, was thus vital in designing and refining the CGJs as DBR interventions, drawing on diverse disciplinary and sectoral perspectives.

Scalability and Adaptability through Glocal Design

The shift from local to glocal jams demonstrated the feasibility and complexity of scaling CGJS across different contexts. Shared themes and digital infrastructures facilitated transnational connectivity, but disciplinary diversity and logistical constraints required modular toolkits and adaptable facilitation models. Therefore, scalability is not about replication but about context-sensitive translation, in which core principles (cultural framing, reflective design, youth agency) are upheld while methods are adapted to local realities.

Outcomes of DBR Across Contexts

In local jams, DBR fostered deep cultural immersion and identity exploration, while glocal jams enhanced civic engagement and systemic thinking. Partners experienced these interventions differently: CHIs discovered new ways to activate heritage; CIs explored value-sensitive design practices; HEIs incorporated game jams into curricula; and young people shifted from participants to cultural agents. These outcomes demonstrate DBR's ability to produce usable knowledge that is both theoretically robust and practically applicable, supporting EPIC-WE's goals of ASSESS, INNOVATE, TRANSFER, and SCALE.

6.7 Meta-Level Reflections

At a higher level, the comparative approach has implications for theory, practice, and policy. Theoretically, it presents CGJs as cultural laboratories – as interventions and enactments of cultural living labs in each site, where heritage is preserved and transformed through play, dialogue, and design. Practically, it

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highlights the importance of transferability and scalability (O3 and O4), showing that while core principles, cultural framing, reflective design, and quadruple helix collaboration are strong, their implementation must remain flexible and adaptable. Relatedly, D4.2 articulates the importance of continuously balancing structure and flexibility as a key trait of collaborative practices in the QH Cultural Hubs (D4.2, p. 31).

In terms of policy, it recognises CGJs as practical tools for democratic participation, youth empowerment, and cultural sustainability, aligning with EU priorities such as the New European Bauhaus and the Sustainable Development Goals. By equipping quadruple helix actors with knowledge, skills, and policy tools, EPIC-WE offers a model for inclusive cultural innovation that is both locally rooted and globally resonant.

In summary, CGJs, whether local or glocal, are not just events but evolving infrastructures for cultural participation. They enable youth to move from being players to cultural agents, heritage institutions to cultural laboratories, and creative industries to civic partners. Through iterative design, reflective practice, and systemic collaboration, these interventions realise the project's objectives and research questions, providing a scalable framework for reimagining Europe's cultural futures.

Ethical Considerations

07

7. Ethical Considerations

Ethics in design research with youth is increasingly recognised as a critical dimension of both scholarly and practical work (van Mechelen, 2020).

Researchers emphasise that ethical considerations are not solely procedural but deeply embedded in the structure and dynamics of participation and design (Antle et al., 2020; Kawas et al., 2020). In EPIC-WE, ethical integrity was addressed holistically, encompassing formal procedural ethics, participation ethics, design ethics, and the more immediate dimensions of everyday and situational ethics (Frauenberger et al., 2017). This multi-layered approach reflects the project's commitment to both compliance and care, ensuring that CGJs function as inclusive, respectful, and reflexive spaces.

7.1 Informed Consent, Participation, and Data Protection

Formal ethics covered all legal, regulatory, and institutional requirements, including GDPR compliance, informed consent, and ethical review processes. Participants received clear information about the purpose, scope, and implications of the research, and consent was obtained from all individuals, including minors, with parental consent, prior to participation. Measures were taken to protect privacy through pseudonymisation and secure data storage. Formal ethics also addressed gender equality and diversity, with procedures in place to handle complaints about discrimination or misconduct in both physical and digital environments, as outlined in WP1 and the project's Grant Agreement.

Data management complied with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and institutional protocols. Personal identifiers were removed or pseudonymised across all datasets, and secure storage systems were applied for both digital and physical records. Access to sensitive data was restricted to authorised researchers, and data-sharing agreements were established for cross-hub collaboration. These measures ensured compliance with legal standards and safeguarded participants' privacy.

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The research design, including CGJ interventions and related data collection, underwent ethical review by relevant institutional committees. This review assessed risks concerning participant well-being, cultural sensitivity, and inclusivity. Ongoing monitoring was maintained throughout the project to address emerging ethical issues, particularly in glocal contexts where cultural norms and expectations differed.

7.2 Participation and Design Ethics

Beyond procedural compliance, EPIC-WE embraced relational ethics by fostering respectful, inclusive, and dialogic engagement. Youth were regarded as co-creators and epistemic partners (Criado & Estalella, 2018; Nørgård & Holflod, 2024), with opportunities to influence and co-decide on themes, design processes, and evaluation criteria. Cultural heritage institutions and creative industry partners were engaged in ways that respected their expertise while promoting fair collaboration. This relational approach was extended to the dissemination phase, where findings were shared in accessible formats to ensure transparency and reciprocity. In sum, ethical considerations in EPIC-WE were not confined to formal protocols but embedded in the project's ethos of participatory cultural innovation, balancing regulatory compliance with care, trust, and mutual respect.

Participation ethics further concern the value of representation and the relational dynamics within the quadruple helix ecosystem. In EPIC-WE, this meant actively engaging stakeholders, CHIs, CIs, HEIs, and youth not only as research subjects but also as co-creators. Ethical participation requires articulating the expected benefits for all actors and aligning activities, such as CGJs, to deliver those benefits. For youth, this included opportunities for skill development, cultural expression, and civic engagement; for institutions, it involved knowledge exchange and capacity-building for innovation. These practices operationalised ethics as a matter of reciprocity and mutual benefit rather than simply compliance.

Design ethics consider the actual and potential effects of games on individuals and society. Games are not neutral objects; they convey messages, values, and

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worldviews that influence player experiences and cultural imaginaries (Sicart, 2011). EPIC-WE incorporated ethical reflection into the design process, enabling youth to consider both intended and unintended consequences from the outset rather than as an afterthought. Facilitators prompted participants to ask: *Whose stories are shown? What values are embedded in mechanics? What cultural narratives are reinforced or challenged?* This proactive approach aligns with value-sensitive design principles and helps create games that encourage critical dialogue rather than perpetuating harmful stereotypes or exclusionary norms.

7.3 Situational and Relational Ethics

Ethical concerns also emerge in the micro-interactions of everyday practice. Everyday ethics in EPIC-WE included observing and addressing issues such as rude behaviour, copyright infringements, and interpersonal tensions during game jams. Situational ethics involve the responsiveness required when unexpected events occur, such as a youth participant showing signs of distress, which may require immediate, context-sensitive action. These moments highlight the importance of reflexivity and adaptability in ethical practice, as argued by Frauenberger et al. (2017). Researchers and facilitators were encouraged to remain attentive to such situations throughout the design and facilitation of the CGJs, with ethical considerations treated as a recurring, reflexive, and integral topic and process rather than something secured through Data Management Plans, informed consent and formal ethics alone. This approach further positioned ethical decision-making as an ongoing, situated practice, embedded in facilitation choices and interactions, rather than as a static checklist to be applied in advance.

Beyond compliance standards, EPIC-WE addressed relational ethics iteratively, focusing on trust, transparency, and care in all interactions. This ethos shaped not only consent processes but also the design of participatory structures, ensuring that youth were regarded as cultural agents rather than passive subjects. Ethical considerations were therefore integrated into the fabric of the project, its governance, facilitation, and design practices, reflecting a commitment to inclusivity, respect, and shared responsibility.

Limitations

08

8. Limitations

Although EPIC-WE successfully advanced its four objectives (ASSESS, INNOVATE, TRANSFER, and SCALE), answered its three overarching research questions (RQ1-RQ3), and delivered significant societal, cultural, and scientific impact, several methodological and strategic limitations must be recognised. Acknowledging these limitations is crucial for further refining the CGJ model and kit, and for ensuring their future alignment and synergies with broader European initiatives such as the New European Bauhaus (NEB), the European Youth Strategy, or the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

8.1 Methodological Constraints

The application of Design-Based Research (DBR) offered a robust methodological framework for iterative design and theory-building, but its complexity posed challenges in maintaining consistency across the QH Cultural Hubs. Variations in institutional ethics protocols, resource availability, and participant demographics affected the comparability and consistent application of reflective DBR practices. While methodological triangulation enhanced validity, reliance on self-reported measures (e.g., surveys, interviews) introduced potential biases, and the short timelines of CGJs limited opportunities to assess youth empowerment and cultural participation over longer periods. These limitations highlight the importance of extending the EPIC-WE results with mixed-method longitudinal designs and integrated evaluation frameworks in future efforts.

8.2 Contextual Variability

Local and glocal CGJ interventions operated within diverse cultural, educational, and infrastructural contexts. Differences in disciplinary backgrounds, institutional rhythms, and technological infrastructures shaped facilitation strategies and creative outputs. While this diversity enriched the project, it also complicated efforts to standardise ecosystems and models for QH Cultural Hubs, CGJ models and Kit, and the creation of games through/for culture. Digital platforms such as Discord and Itch.io enabled cross-hub and transnational collaboration but introduced cognitive and technical burdens for participants

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unfamiliar with online communication and collaboration environments. These challenges highlight the importance of adaptive infrastructure and capacity-building for facilitators to ensure equitable participation across QH Cultural Hubs and CGJ contexts.

8.3 Strategic and Policy-Level Gaps

EPIC-WE successfully addressed Horizon Europe synergies, including participation in the Games for Culture Cluster (GCC) and formal collaboration agreements with universities and other EU projects. These partnerships enhanced knowledge exchange and positioned CGJs within a broader cultural innovation ecosystem. However, structural mechanisms for sustained integration into policy frameworks and industry practices remain underdeveloped. While CGJs demonstrated potential to embed heritage in cultural-creative value chains and to inspire CHI and CI uptake, formal pathways for scaling these practices, through Creative Europe, NEB Labs, or Horizon Europe clusters, require further consolidation or institutionalisation. Similarly, youth involvement in governance, though improved through advisory boards, remained largely consultative or participatory rather than fully co-decisional, somewhat limiting the full potential to position youth as future leaders and decision-makers in cultural heritage and games development.

8.4 Reflections for Future Iterations

To address these limitations and increase future impact, research and practice should:

- Extend intervention timelines beyond singular projects to enable deeper cultural heritage integration and allow for deeper longitudinal impact assessment.
- Further develop the EPIC-WE CGJ model and Kit, along with its facilitation protocols, to disseminate the developed and tested core principles while adapting to local context realities.
- Implement Youth Advisory Boards and involve youth as core partners in QH Cultural Hubs to further institutionalise and support youth co-

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- governance frameworks within CHIs, CIs, and HEIs, and to ensure genuine participation in decision-making going forward.
- Further enhance industry collaborations through building on the EPIC-WE QH Cultural Hub model as co-creation cultural living labs, encouraging the adoption of heritage- and value-sensitive game-making and culture-making.
 - Further formalise the integration of QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs into EU policy agendas and funding streams (Creative Europe, Horizon Europe, NEB Labs) to secure the sustainability and systemic adoption of the results and innovations developed, tested, and evaluated in the EPIC-WE project.

Recognising these limitations does not diminish EPIC-WE's contributions; instead, it highlights the complexity of creating sustainable participatory cultural innovation ecosystems and emphasises the importance of iterative, adaptable, and policy-linked strategies. By building on the EPIC-WE results and addressing these gaps, future initiatives can fully unlock the transformative potential of QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs as scalable ecosystems and models for cultural participation, youth empowerment, and inclusive innovation in games and culture across Europe.

Conclusion & Good Practice Recommendations

09

9. Conclusion and Good Practice Recommendations

The EPIC-WE project demonstrates that CGJs embedded in QH Cultural Hubs are effective new formats for participatory cultural innovation, youth empowerment, and value-sensitive game design, drawing on national and European cultural heritage, including EU values. Synthesising insights from twelve CGJ interventions across local and glocal strands, three key findings addressed the research questions and objectives.

9.1 Key Insights and Answers to RQ1–RQ3

- **RQ1 – Games as Cultural Worlds:**
Games created in CGJs, through or for culture, function as cultural worlds that explore, play with, imagine, create, and reflect social themes, cultural heritage, and values. They enable youth to explore participation, identity, voice, belonging, and democracy through interactive, collaborative game design and gameplay. Integrating heritage and values was strongest when they were embedded in the games' mechanics, narratives, aesthetics, and game worlds rather than remaining declarative.
- **RQ2 – Role of CHIs and CIs:**
Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs) and Creative Industries (CIs) are pivotal in facilitating inclusive, value-sensitive CGJs. CHIs provide cultural depth and framing of heritage and values; CIs contribute technical and design expertise and creative mentorship. Effective facilitation requires adaptive frameworks, scaffolded reflection, and informal trust-building interactions (as observed in the QH Cultural Hub ecosystem and the application and evaluation of the CGJ model and Kit).
- **RQ3 – Youth as Cultural Agents:**
CGJs empower youth to transition from consumers to participants by taking up roles as game-makers, culture-makers, and civic actors. Public exhibitions of games through/for culture, Youth Advisory Boards, and culturally reflective game design processes validate their contributions as cultural work. Empowerment was most evident when youth were scaffolded as game-makers and culture-makers, yet still experienced creative agency and autonomy, engaged creatively or critically with

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heritage and values, and were recognised as equal partners in the CGJs and QH Cultural Hubs.

9.2 Achievement of Project Objectives (O1–O4)

- **O1 (ASSESS):** Demonstrated the cultural and civic potential of game-making as culture-making through empirical evidence of youth empowerment and cultural participation in CGJs and QH Cultural Hubs.
- **O2 (INNOVATE):** Developed and validated the Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem, QH Cultural Hub, CGJ model and Kit, games through/for culture, and game-making as culture-making, integrating cultural, technical, and civic dimensions for empowered participation.
- **O3 (TRANSFER):** Captured the developed innovations as open-access models, kits, and cultural games collections on the EPIC-WE Resource Site, along with open-access research, reports, protocols, and guidelines on the EPIC-WE project site to enable replication and scalability across diverse contexts.
- **O4 (SCALE):** Developed, tested, and evaluated CGJs at a scale through 12 CGJ interventions across three QH Cultural Hubs involving more than 400 youth, creating more than 100 cultural game prototypes, informing strategies for embedding and scaling these results within European cultural and educational infrastructures.

9.3 Good Practice Recommendations for Future Research, Policy, and Practice

Building on the EPIC-WE project’s local, glocal, and comparative analyses (Sections 4–6) and the broader literature on Design-Based Research, heritage- and value-sensitive game design, and quadruple helix ecosystems/living labs, we distil a set of evidence-informed recommendations that are both actionable and scalable. These recommendations align with EPIC-WE’s objectives (ASSESS, INNOVATE, TRANSFER, SCALE) and directly address recurrent patterns observed across QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs: embedding values and heritage in games, institutionalising youth agency, and stabilising cross-sector collaboration through ecosystems, models and kits along with policy instruments (Barab & Squire, 2004; Brown, 1992; Costa et al., 2025; Eriksson et

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al., 2024; Fuglsang et al., 2021; Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2014; Schuurman et al., 2015; Sicart, 2011, 2023; Steen & van Bueren, 2017).

Research directions. Findings from the local and glocal strands indicate that values and heritage are sometimes applied superficially or declaratively rather than deeply integrated or operative within the game. Future applications of cultural heritage and values in game-making should therefore ensure that methods and tools for incorporating culture and values are sufficiently scaffolded and facilitated (e.g. using the CGJ Kit or similar resources), that equal participation is encoded through tailored starting resources, negotiated authority, and trade-off mechanics (e.g. Youth Advisory Boards or including youth as partners), and that those patterns are examined as they travel across contexts (Costa et al., 2025; Eriksson et al., 2025). As short, intense interventions or projects reduce the probability of wider impacts or long-term outcomes, more longitudinal mixed-method approaches (3+ years) that track shifts in empowered participation, cultural identity development, and institutional adoption over semesters or academic years (Barab & Squire, 2004; Brown, 1992) should be used.

Additionally, this should include communication infrastructures for glocal cross-sector collaboration: Discord, itch.io, or similar platforms that support dialogue, sharing, and reflection without adding cognitive load, as well as youth co-governance models like QH Cultural Hubs or Youth Advisory Boards that move youth beyond end-user or consultative roles to partnership and participatory decision-making in game-making and culture-making (Nørgård & Holflod, 2024; Schütz et al., 2019).

Policy integration. To address the strategic gaps identified in Section 9.3 – particularly structural mechanisms for long-term impact and outcomes – QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs should be recognised or supported within European cultural and innovation frameworks (e.g. Creative Europe, NEB Labs, Horizon Europe clusters). This recommendation builds on evidence from Sections 6.2 and 6.5, which show that glocal QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs successfully scaled cross-sector and youth participation and co-creation in culture but lacked

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systemic continuity. Policy instruments should include multi-annual grants or innovation/development support for cross-sector culture hubs and culture jams that involve youth as partners to incentivise CHI–CI–HEI–youth partnerships and make QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs sustainable beyond project timelines (Sections 4.2 and 5.2). Implementation and evaluation should privilege deep integration of cultural heritage and values in games through/for culture, and in their gameplay interaction and experience, to avoid superficial application (Sections 5.2 and 6.3). Finally, policy frameworks must continue to fund Open Access and accessibility-by-design for ecosystems, models, toolkits and resources to promote empowered participation in game-making and culture-making, aligning with the ethical commitments outlined in Section 8 (Antle et al., 2020; Van Mechelen et al., 2020).

Practice and implementation. While the insights and syntheses presented in this report, and thus the recommendations, are numerous, three actionable insights across hubs provide practical levers for sustained quality in and around CGJs and collaborative partnerships:

- 1. Modular toolkits and scaffolded integration.** Toolkits should be flexible and modular for diverse cohorts (e.g., culture, media, or design studies vs. computer science) and integrate scaffolded processes and methods for exploration, imagination, experimentation, and reflection – including transition tools and checkpoints for moving between these phases (as in the CGJ Kit) (Sections 4.2 and 5.2). Such an approach demonstrably improved cultural integration and youth agency, especially when the toolkit and processes were properly grounded in heritage-sensitive approaches – e.g., creating games through culture using cultural heritage sites, archives, collections, or artefacts as concrete game-making material for – and value-sensitive approaches – e.g., creating games for culture using value cards, civic imagination, or societal themes (Eriksson et al., 2024; Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2014).
- 2. Youth Advisory Boards and youth as partners.** YABs and including youth as partners in QH Cultural Hubs were important in strengthening youth participation, voice, and belonging; however, empowerment

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remained unevenly distributed in the QH Cultural Hubs and CGJs. We recommend institutionalising YAB participation and including youth as partners in QH Cultural Hubs from the outset (or similar youth empowerment mechanisms), co-creating the processes and themes, co-defining evaluation criteria, and co-curating public exhibitions, so youth act as core partners in the QH Cultural Hubs or events (Sections 4.2 and 6.3; Nørgård & Holflod, 2024; Holflod et al., 2024).

3. **Spatial choreography and cross-sector facilitation.** Engagement and participation increased at inspirational sites where heritage was directly accessible as game jam material (museums, digital archives, cities, game studios), and prototyping quality improved in resource-rich, co-creative settings. It is recommended to carefully curate and frame the use of heritage sites, venues, materials and values to protect the interplay of “scaffolded integration” and larger “just making” windows, plan transitions carefully, and combine cultural integration (CHI) with game-making mentorship (CI) and pedagogical scaffolding (HEI). This balance reduces friction and helps translate inspiration into thoughtful, reflexive, and innovative games through/for culture (Sections 4.1–5.2; Keogh & Hardwick, 2023; Sicart, 2011, 2023).

In sum, games become, and are experienced as, cultural worlds when heritage and values are embedded in the gameplay system, interaction, and experience, rather than applied as superficial add-on elements (Sections 4–6; Costa et al., 2025; Eriksson et al., 2025; Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2014; Sicart, 2011). To achieve this shift in cultural game design practice, the field must advance through research and interventions that track cultural participation and agency over time; policies that institutionalise helix-based cross-sector collaboration and youth partnerships and co-governance; and implementation strategies that operationalise modular toolkits, scaffolded processes, and deliberate heritage choreography to ensure both culture-making and game-making. Taken together, these recommendations translate EPIC-WE’s insights into scalable innovations and infrastructures for cultural participation, innovation, and empowerment, aligning with European priorities on inclusion, democratic participation, and

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cultural sustainability (Fuglsang et al., 2021; Schuurman et al., 2015; Steen & van Bueren, 2017).

Looking ahead, advancing the cultural and civic dimensions of game-making requires moving beyond isolated interventions towards systemic, research-informed interventions and infrastructures. Rather than reinforcing existing practices, future work should consolidate and extend the results and recommendations that EPIC-WE has proven effective, and address unresolved tensions: embedding values and heritage deeply into gameplay systems, interactions, and experience rather than relegating them to an appendix or add-on. It should also ensure and sustain youth agency beyond consultancy or advisory roles, and balance creative freedom with scaffolded cultural framing. This means developing transdisciplinary studies of game-making as culture-making and of games as cultural worlds, examining how heritage and values can travel across contexts (Sections 4–6), and piloting longitudinal models that track cultural agency and empowerment, as well as institutional adoption, over time. It also calls for curricular integration and contextual design of CGJs as participatory cultural learning formats, supported by inclusive, heritage- and value-sensitive design and modular CGJ Kits.

For cultural institutions and creative industries, the challenge is to combine game-making, culture-making, and cultural heritage with creative value chains, not as one-off events but as repeated, co-governed processes across sectors, supported by open resources, accessibility-by-design, and long-term support from QH Cultural Hub. These steps transform CGJs from tested cultural-creative models into living cultural laboratories, ensuring that youth move from consumers to cultural agents and creators and that Europe's cultural ecosystems evolve towards more participatory, empowered, and sustainable futures.

References

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10. References

- Antle, A. N., Frauenberger, C., Landoni, M., Fails, J. A., Jirotko, M., Webb, H., & Tutiya-phuengprasert, N. (2020, June). Emergent, situated and prospective ethics for child-computer interaction research. In Proceedings of the 2020 ACM Interaction Design and Children Conference: Extended Abstracts, 54-61.
- Barab, S., & Squire, K. (2004). Design-based research: Putting a stake in the ground. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 13(1), 1–14.
https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327809jls1301_1
- Barwick, J., Dearnley, J., & Muir, A. (2011). Playing Games With Cultural Heritage: A Comparative Case Study Analysis of the Current Status of Digital Game Preservation. *Games and Culture*, 6(4), 373-390.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1555412010391092> (Original work published 2011)
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. Sage.
- Brown, A. L. (1992). Design experiments: Theoretical and methodological challenges in creating complex interventions. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 2(2), 141–178.
- Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. J. (2012). *Mode 3 Knowledge Production in Quadruple Helix Innovation Systems. SpringerBriefs in Business* (vol. 7). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-2062-0_1
- Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. (2022). Towards an emerging unified theory of helix architectures (EUTOHA): Focus on the quintuple innovation helix
- Cobb, P., Confrey, J., diSessa, A., Lehrer, R., & Schauble, L. (2003). Design Experiments in Educational Research. *Educational Researcher*, 32(1), 9-13.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X032001009>
- Costa, C., Holflod, K., Nørgård, R. T., Gonçalves, M., Nunes, I., & Fernandes, P. (2025). Exploring Cultural Game-Making With Youth: A 20-Year Systematic Review. *Games and Culture*, 0(0).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/15554120251382358>
- Costa, C., Fernandes, P., Nunes, I., Gonçalves, M., & Fonseca, M. (2024a). Report on good practices - Game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654105>
- Costa, C., Fernandes, P., Nunes, I., Gonçalves, M., & Fonseca, M. (2024b). *State of the Art in game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst*

D2.3 Synthesis of EPIC-WE Outcomes

Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14654424>

- Costa, C., Car, V., & Papadimitriou, S. (2017). Good practices and emerging trends in media and information literacy. In J. F. Michel, D. Frau-Meigs, & I. Velez (Eds.), *Public Policies in Media and Information Literacy in Europe* (1st ed., pp. 227–268). Routledge.
- <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315628851-8>
- Criado, T. S., & Estalella, A. (2018). Introduction – Experimental Collaborations. *Experimental Collaborations: Ethnography through Fieldwork Devices* (s. 1-16). Berghahn Books. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781785338540-004>
- Edelson, D. C. (2002). Design Research: What We Learn When We Engage in Design. *Journal of the Learning Sciences*, 11(1), 105–121.
- https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327809JLS1101_4
- Eriksson, E., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T. (2024). Creative toying with cultural heritage in game jams. In *ICGJ'24: Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Game Jams, Hackathons and Game Creation Events* (pp. 9–16). Association for Computing Machinery.
- <https://doi.org/10.1145/3697789.3697795>
- Eriksson, E., Costa, C., Goncalves, M., Nunes, I., Groen, M., Niederer, S., Holflod, K., & Nørgård, R. T. (2025). Cultural game jams with youth: A multiple-site case study. In *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA'25'25)*, April 26-May 1, 2025, Yokohama, Japan (8 pages). Association for Computing Machinery.
- <https://doi.org/10.1145/3706599.3706667>
- Flanagan, M., & Nissenbaum, H. (2014). *Values at play in digital games*. MIT Press.
- Frauenberger, C., Rauhala, M., & Fitzpatrick, G. (2017). In-Action Ethics. *Interacting with Computers*, 29(2), 220–236.
- <https://doi.org/10.1093/iwc/iww024>
- Fuglsang, L., Hansen, A. V., Mergel, I., & Røhnebæk, M. T. (2021). Living labs for public sector innovation: An integrative literature review. *Administrative Sciences*, 11(2), 58. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci11020058>
- Holflod, K., Nørgård, R. T., & Eriksson, E. (2024). Community, socialisation, and empowerment in cultural game jams with youth citizens. In *Proceedings of the 18th European Conference on Games Based Learning* (Vol. 18, pp. 395–402). Academic Conferences and Publishing International.
- <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecgbl.18.1.2812>

D2.3 Synthesis of EPIC-WE Outcomes

- Kawas, S., Yuan, Y., DeWitt, A., Jin, Q., Kirchner, S., Bilger, A., Grantham, E., Kientz, J.A., Tartaro, A. & Yarosh, S. (2020). Another decade of IDC research: Examining and reflecting on values and ethics. In Proceedings of the interaction design and children conference, 205-215.
- Keogh, B., & Hardwick, T. (2023). Creative, technical, entrepreneurial: Formative tensions in game development higher education. *Games and Culture*, 19(6), 804–826. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15554120231176874>
- McKenney, S., & Reeves, T. C. (2019). *Conducting educational design research* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Nørgård, R. T., & Holflod, K. (2024). Meeting in the middle: Cultural co-creation, transformative partnerships, and ecosystems for public good. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 57(2), 112-127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2024.2384722>
- Schuurman, D., De Marez, L., & Ballon, P. (2015). Living labs: A systematic literature review. Open Living Lab Days 2015, Proceedings. Presented at the Open Living Lab Days 2015. <http://hdl.handle.net/1854/LU-7026155>
- Schütz, F., Heidingsfelder, M. L., & Schraudner, M. (2019). Co-shaping the future in quadruple helix innovation systems: Uncovering public preferences toward participatory research and innovation. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 5(2), 128–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2019.04.002>
- Sicart, M. (2011). *The ethics of computer games*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Sicart, M. A. (2023). *Playing Software: Homo Ludens in Computational Culture*. MIT Press.
- Somers Miles, R., Koppelman, W., Lennaerts, K., Sabine Niederer, De Gaetano, C., Groen, M., Dockett, A., Eriksson, E., & Holflod, K. (2024). Protocol 3: EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites (Initial protocol). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13886222>
- Somers Miles, R., Koppelman, W., Niederer, S., De Gaetano, C., Groen, M., Catalano, V., Dockett, A., Eriksson, E., & Holflod, K. (2025). Protocol 3: EPIC-WE Research Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Local Sites. (Final protocol).
- Steen, K., & van Bueren, E. (2017). The defining characteristics of urban living labs. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 7(7), 21–33. <https://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/1088>
- Taratori, R., Rodriguez-Fiscal, P., Pacho, M. A., Koutra, S., Pareja-Eastaway, M., & Thomas, D. (2021). Unveiling the evolution of innovation ecosystems: An analysis of triple, quadruple, and quintuple helix model innovation systems

D2.3 Synthesis of EPIC-WE Outcomes

in european case studies. Sustainability (Switzerland), 13(14), Article 7582. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147582>

van Mechelen, M., Baykal, G. E., Dindler, C., Eriksson, E., & Iversen, O. S. (2020, June). 18 years of ethics in child-computer interaction research: A systematic literature review. In Proceedings of the ACM Interaction Design and Children Conference, 161-183.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3392063.3394407>

von Hippel, E. (2006). Democratizing innovation. MIT Press

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